

ASTRAL

All Atlantic Ocean Sustainable, ProfiTable and Resilient AquacuLture

GA no **863034**

Research and Innovation Action (RIA)

Start date: 1st September 2020. End date: 30th September 2024

D2.4 New value chain at IMTA lab South Africa

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 863034

Disclaimer: This material reflects only the author's view and the Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Document administration

Deliverable number	D2.4
Deliverable name	New value chain at IMTA lab South Africa
WP number	WP2
Deliverable due date	31/05/2024
Submission date	05/06/2024
Dissemination levels	Public
Lead beneficiary	UCT, DFFE
Responsible	Brett Macey
Contributors	Brett Macey, Marissa Brink-Hull, John Bolton – UCT, DFFE Marina Sandoval, Pablo Sanchez Cueto – LEITAT
Internal reviewers	Luis Poersch, Tomás Chalde, Elisa Ravagnan

Document history and changes

Document history			
Version	Date	Modified by	Comments
1.0	15.02.2024	Brett Macey	Table of contents to to WP Leader (WPL), to reviewers and Project Coordinator (PC)
1.1	31.03.2024	Brett Macey (DFFE), John Bolton (UCT), Marissa Brink-Hull (UCT)	Advanced draft to WPL, Reviewers and PC
1.2	30.04.2024	Internal Reviewers	Final draft to WPL, Reviewers and PC
1.3	15.05.2024	Internal Reviewers	Reviewers return the document proofread and commented to the author(s)
1.4	31.05.2024	Internal Reviewers	Final Version

Evidence of accomplishment

Report

Contents

1. Summary	4
2. List of figures and tables	7
3. Introduction	13
3.1. ASTRAL.....	13
3.2. IMTA in land-based partially recirculated systems in South Africa	13
3.3. IMTA Lab South Africa – Land-based pump ashore system	15
3.3.1. Site Description.....	15
3.3.2. Cultivation Environment.....	18
4. IMTA species	19
4.1 Abalone <i>Haliotis midae</i> integrated with <i>Ulva lacinulata</i>	19
4.1.1 Introduction	19
4.1.2 Trial Methodology.....	21
4.1.3 Results.....	26
4.1.4 Discussion and Conclusion.....	43
4.2 Urchin <i>Tripneustes gratilla</i> integrated with <i>Ulva lacinulata</i>	46
4.2.1 Introduction	46
4.2.2 Trial Methodology.....	48
4.2.3 Results.....	53
4.2.4 Discussion and Conclusion.....	67
4.3 Urchin <i>Parechinus angulosus</i> integrated with juvenile abalone <i>Haliotis midae</i>	73
4.3.1 Introduction	73
4.3.2 Trial Methodology.....	74
4.3.3 Results.....	79
4.3.4 Discussion and Conclusion.....	87
5. ASTRAL IMTA Production Species/Production Value Chain	89
6. Acknowledgements.....	93

1. Summary

This deliverable was created as part of the WP2 ‘New IMTA value chains and production methods’ of the H2020 All Atlantic Ocean Sustainable, Profitable and Resilient Aquaculture (ASTRAL) project and deals with the production value chain of IMTA Lab South Africa (Figure 1; adapted from Bostock et al.¹). Other aspects of the value chain are addressed in investigations and reports compiled by other Work Packages in ASTRAL (see ASTRAL deliverables 4.1, 4.4, 6.3, 7.7, etc.). The deliverable provides information on all the trials undertaken for each of the species produced or introduced at IMTA Lab South Africa.

Figure 1. Shaded area indicates the section of the aquaculture production value chain covered by IMTA Lab South Africa.

The overall objective of IMTA Lab South Africa was to develop and validate cost-effective IMTA in land-based pump ashore systems with partial recirculation. To achieve this objective, the physical and chemical parameters as well as the microbial community of an existing fully commercial abalone (*Haliotis midae*)-*Ulva lacinulata* IMTA system was monitored to provide critical information on biosecurity, species health and system health. The possibility of increasing recirculation rates in the existing IMTA, from 50% to 75% and 100% recirculation, was also investigated. Culture technology for the production of a new high value species, the collector sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla*, was

¹ Bostock J., Lane A., Hough C., et al., 2016. An assessment of the economic contribution of EU aquaculture production and the influence of policies for its sustainable development. *Aquaculture International* 24: 699-733.

developed and optimised in IMTA, and potential for using faecal matter from the Cape sea urchin *Parechinus angulosus* as a feed/probiotic for juvenile abalone was investigated.

Clear daily rhythms in oxygen, pH, temperature, and nutrients were observed in the integrated abalone-*Ulva* IMTA. Daytime temperatures and passage of effluent water through *Ulva* paddle raceways in the IMTA results in warming and increased oxygen in the daytime. Seawater pH was shown to be higher in the day than at night, with maximum dissolved ammonia nitrogen concentrations observed early in the morning (due to the great metabolic activity of abalone at night) — with a strong negative correlation observed between FAN removal and pH. At standard 50% recirculation, total ammonia nitrogen removal across the seaweed biofilters ranged from 65-85% (mean 73%). Total ammonia nitrogen (TAN) and FAN levels were consistently low at 50% recirculation (<1 mg.L⁻¹), variable at 75% recirculation (<1 to >3 mg.L⁻¹) and high (6 mg.L⁻¹) at the end of the 3-day 100% recirculation trial. There were no significant differences between the 50% and 75% recirculation clusters for temperature, pH, TAN or FAN. At 100% recirculation, temperature was consistently 1°C higher in the daytime, and pH was around 1 unit lower throughout. Also at 100%, TAN and FAN increased rapidly. Data indicated that the IMTA could feasibly run for extended periods at 75% recirculation, with relatively little effect on water quality compared with 50% recirculation. Although no adverse health effects were observed on the abalone when the system was run at 100% recirculation for 3-days, ammonia reached critical levels (from literature values) on the third day. The lack of obvious effects on the abalone suggests there is potential to use *Ulva*'s bioremediation capacity to mitigate the effects of harmful algal blooms over at least 2-3 days of a bloom event.

The microbiome studies revealed that the inclusion of *Ulva* in IMTA systems results in beneficial changes in the microbiome of water and farmed abalone by reducing the presence of opportunistic pathogens. When assessing the bacterial community dynamics with increasing recirculation rates, the taxonomic composition of the samples varied across sampling points, suggesting that recirculation at higher rates (50%, 75% & 100%) has an effect on the microbiome composition, but does not result in an increase in opportunistic bacteria. Inclusion of *Ulva* or components of *Ulva* in formulated feeds for farmed abalone was shown to have a beneficial effect on the abalone gut microbiome, reducing abundance of opportunistic bacteria, with a corresponding increase in beneficial bacteria. Investigations to assess the use of faecal matter from the Cape sea urchin *Parechinus angulosus* as a feed/probiotic for juvenile abalone revealed that supplementing juvenile abalone diets with sea urchin faecal matter is advantageous for abalone growth and health in their early juvenile stages, possibly as a result of microbial community transfer from the sea urchins.

Trials to optimise culture technology of the collector sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla* revealed that deeper baskets result in significantly lower consumption of various feed types — likely the

consequence of lower feed accessibility. Furthermore, removal of urchin baskets from tanks for extended periods (5-minutes) or feeding rigid feed types (e.g., *E. maxima*) results in increased spine loss, suggesting consumption and removal of baskets for extended periods are the primary cause of decreased production in deeper baskets. While higher stocking densities (8 kg.m⁻²) significantly reduced mass SGR (P<0.044), urchin mortality, cannibalism and gonad size/quality were not influenced at lower stocking densities tested (4 and 6 kg.m⁻²). Differences in SGR are attributed to spine loss from negative behavioural interactions. To maximise total urchin mass and gonad yield, stocking densities of approximately 20% coverage of the internal surface area of baskets are recommended. Trials showed that it is possible to feed urchins fresh IMTA grown *Ulva* during the somatic growth phase, and that feeding with protein rich formulated feeds is only required during the gonad enhancement phase to bulk gonads prior to market. To further streamline production and reduce stress on cultured urchins, a computer vision protocol was developed that significantly increases the precision and decreases the time required for estimating average urchin diameter and mass in a commercial setting. Trials further concluded that careful consideration must be made with regards to site selection when farming *T. gratilla*, as hypo-saline conditions (<30 ppt) increase stress and reduce disease resistance of this species. Therefore, sites located close to estuaries where salinities are either periodically or frequently impacted by rainfall events should be avoided.

In conclusion, trials at IMTA Lab South Africa have provided valuable information on the biosecurity, species health and system health of the existing abalone-*Ulva* IMTA with 50% recirculation. Critical information on the physical and chemical parameters as well as the microbial community of the IMTA was generated that could promote broader uptake of IMTA by local and international producers and enhance the sustainability of this production species/value chain. Culture technology for commercial scale production of a new high value species, the collector sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla*, in IMTA has been development and further optimised, and the benefits of using faecal matter from the Cape sea urchin *Parechinus angulosus* as a feed/probiotic for juvenile abalone has been clearly demonstrated — resulting in enhanced growth and health of juvenile abalone. These findings have contributed towards the development of new, sustainable, profitable, and resilient value chains for IMTA production within the ASTRAL project and within the framework of existing, emerging and potential Atlantic markets.

2. List of figures and tables

Figure 1. Shaded area indicates the section of the aquaculture production value chain covered by IMTA Lab South Africa.	4
Figure 2. Land-based pump ashore IMTA system to produce abalone (<i>Haliotis midae</i>) and seaweed (<i>Ulva lacinulata</i>) at Buffeljags Abalone Farm. (A) Aerial photograph of the modular abalone- <i>Ulva</i> IMTA (©Viking Aquaculture). (B) Schematic of the IMTA process in a single abalone- <i>Ulva</i> cluster (©Brett Macey).	16
Figure 3. Species cultivated at the South African IMTA Lab. (A) South African abalone, <i>Haliotis midae</i> (© John Bolton); (B) sea lettuce, <i>Ulva lacinulata</i> (© Mark Cyrus); (C) collector sea urchin, <i>Tripneustes gratilla</i> (© Bas de Vos); and (D) Cape urchin, <i>Parechinus angulosus</i> (© Marissa Brink-Hull).	18
Figure 4. Location of IMTA Lab South Africa — Buffeljags Abalone Farm (© Brett Macey).	19
Figure 5. Temperature (°C) trend for 50% (21/07/21 – 24/08/21) and 75% (24/08/21 – 27/09/21) recirculation trials (A), accompanied by the daily trends in temperature over the last 72 hours of testing for all recirculation rates. (100% recirculation 08/11/2021 – 10-11/2021) (B).....	27
Figure 6. The pH (pH units) trend for the 50% (21/07/21 – 24/08/21) and 75% (24/08/21 – 27/09/21) recirculation trials (A), accompanied by the daily trends in pH over the last 72 hours of testing for all recirculation rates (B).	28
Figure 7. Nutrient concentration ($\mu\text{M.L}^{-1}$) in the morning (A) and the afternoon (B) at 50% recirculation, where each week three measurements, one from each cluster (clusters 2.1, 2.2, and 3.1), were taken from the outlet of the abalone raceway, on the same day, from the 21/07/21-11/08/21, as well as at 75% recirculation in the morning (C) and the afternoon (D) where each new week three measurements, one from each cluster (clusters 2.1, 2.2 and 3.1), were taken from the outlet of the abalone raceway 18/08/21-18/08/21.	29
Figure 8. Boxplots showing the range of nutrient concentration ($\mu\text{M.L}^{-1}$) for 50% and 75% recirculation (outlet concentrations) (A), 75% (outlet concentrations) and 100% (inlet and outlet concentrations) recirculation (B) and 50% (control inlet and outlet concentrations) and 100% (inlet and outlet concentrations) recirculation (C). The box represents the interquartile range (IQR), the middle line represents the median and the whiskers represent 1.5x IQR or range if less than these values, the points represent outliers.	30
Figure 9. The 100% recirculation nutrient concentrations ($\mu\text{M.L}^{-1}$), where measurements were taken from each cluster every four hours (2.1, 2.2, and 3.1), and a control cluster (3.2) that was running at 50% recirculation during the day (8 AM-4 PM) going into the abalone raceway (A) and out of the abalone raceway (B) as well as nutrient concentrations during the night (8 PM to 4 AM) going into (C) and out of (D) the abalone raceway from the 8/11/21 to the 11/11/21.	32

Figure 10. Boxplot comparing the difference between inlet and outlet nutrient concentrations ($\mu\text{M/l}$) between 50% and 100% recirculation rates. The box represents the interquartile range (IQR), the middle line represents the median and the whiskers represent 1.5x IQR or range if less than these values, the points represent outliers. 33

Figure 11. Daily variation in TAN (A) and FAN (B) concentrations (mg.L^{-1}) over the period (8/11/21 - 11/11/21) of intensive monitoring where TAN measurements were recorded every four hours in both the 100% recirculation and the 50% control recirculation. 34

Figure 12. Daily average FAN and TAN concentrations (mg.L^{-1}) over the period where measurements were taken from each cluster once a week in the morning and afternoon on the same day for three clusters (2.1, 2.2, and 2.3) for both 50% and 75% recirculation. The 100% recirculation are daily averages over four days of continuous testing, where measurements were taken from each cluster (2.1, 2.2, and 3.1) every four hours. 35

Figure 13. Dissolved oxygen concentrations (mg.L^{-1}) measured every two hours during intensive monitoring (8/11/21- 11/11/21) for both 50% and 100% recirculation. 36

Figure 14. Relative amplicon sequence variant (ASV) abundance at genus level across the 60 samples from the South African lab. The 30 most abundant ASVs are depicted and the remaining ASVs were grouped as "Others". Non-IMTA=seawater system; IMTA=abalone effluent water system. 37

Figure 15. Non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS), computed from Bray-Curtis distance matrix and grouped by sample (inlet, outlet and *Ulva*) and system type (SW=seawater/non-IMTA system; AEW=abalone effluent water/IMTA system. 38

Figure 16. Within-sample diversity represented by the Shannon index across samples collected in this trial (inlet, outlet, sediment, *Ulva* and abalone intestine). Colour indicates sampling timepoints representing the different recirculation rates (50, 75, 100). 39

Figure 17. Principal Component analyses (PCoA), computed from Bray-Curtis distance matrix and grouped by sample (inlet, outlet, sediment, *Ulva* and abalone intestine) and recirculation (50, 75, 100) at Buffeljags Abalone Farm. 40

Figure 18. Bar graph showing the relative (%) amplified sequence variant (ASV) abundance at phylum level across the different sample types (inlet, outlet, sediment, *Ulva* and abalone intestine) and recirculation rates (50, 75 and 100) assessed in this trial. Colours represent the 10 most abundant phyla, where "Others" represents the remaining phyla. 40

Figure 19. Average relative (%) abundance of bacterial genera observed in the intestines of abalone fed different diets ($n = 5$ per diet), where the top 30 genera are listed and the remaining genera are denoted as "Others". 41

Figure 20. Venn diagram of the bacterial communities associated with the intestines of abalone fed different diets, showing limited compositional difference between the respective groups with the exception of fresh *Ulva* fed animals having less shared ASVs with the other groups (AB – formulated; ABFU – formulated supplemented with fresh *Ulva*; AB10U – formulated with 10% dried *Ulva* inclusion; AB1U – formulated with 1% *Ulva* inclusion; AB0.1G – formulated with 0.1% glucuronic acid inclusion; FU – fresh *Ulva*)..... 42

Figure 21. Average daily spine loss of *Tripnesutes gratilla* maintained in either shallow (15cm) or deep (30cm) baskets (A) when fed three different feed types, namely kelp (*Ecklonia maxima*), a pelleted formulated feed, or fresh *Ulva lacinulata* and (B) in response to three different basket removal treatments, including none (not removed from the water), short (five-second removal daily) and long (five-minute removal daily). The different subscripts above each box plot represent significant differences between the mean spine loss of urchins within each treatment group..... 54

Figure 22. The average daily consumption of the pelleted formulated feed (A) and fresh *Ulva lacinulata* (B) by *Tripneustes gratilla* housed in deep (30cm) and shallow (15cm) baskets (C). Different subscripts above the box plots represent significant differences in consumption between treatments. 55

Figure 23. The effect of low (4 kgs.m⁻²), medium (6 kgs.m⁻²) and high (8 kgs.m⁻²) stocking densities on (A) the mass specific growth rate (SGR) of *Tripneustes gratilla*, (B) the total mass of all urchins in a basket (B), and the net predicted gonad yield (g.m⁻² basket ISA) over a period of three months. Different subscripts above box plots represent significant differences between the means of treatment groups..... 56

Figure 24. Logarithmic function representing the percentage reduction in mass averaged between nine urchins weighed at various times following removal from a body of water ($y = -0.013\ln(x) + 1.0153$, $R^2 = 0.97$). The percentage value was determined by dividing the mass of each urchin at individual time points by its initial mass at five seconds. 57

Figure 25. Box plots comparing the distribution of coefficient of variation between various measurement methods for *Tripneustes gratilla*. M.O. = multiple operators, S.O. = single operator, and T.B. = total basket mass. Different subscripts denote a significant difference in the coefficients of variation between methods (Height measurements were not included in the statistical analysis, hence there are no subscripts above the box plots). 58

Figure 26. Coelomic fluid salinity (ppt) (A) and the righting activity coefficient ($AC = 1000 \times s^{-1}$) (B) of *Tripnesutes gratilla* acutely exposed (over a period of 1-hour) to four hypo-saline treatments (30, 25, 20 and 15ppt salinity), hypersaline treatment (40ppt), and a control treatment (35ppt salinity). 59

Figure 27. Mean number of culturable bacteria remaining in haemolymph circulation of *Tripneustes gratilla* in each treatment at 30-minutes post-challenge with *Vibrio anguillarum*. Values are mean \pm

S.E. (n=6-18 samples). Different letters indicate a significant difference (P<0.05) between treatments (Holm-Sidak multiple comparison). 59

Figure 28. Land-based pump-ashore IMTA system for the production of sea urchin (*Tripneustes gratilla*) and seaweed (*Ulva lacinulata*) at Buffeljags abalone. The photograph shows (A) the 8000 L glass fibre raceway tanks housing sea urchins; (B) the drum filter, protien skimmers, and sump; (C) *Ulva* paddle raceway; and (D) tunnel system housing all the aforementioned system components.. 60

Figure 29. Mean±SEM diameter (A) and feed consumption (%BW.day⁻¹) of *Tripneustes gratilla* fed with three experimental diets: FF= Formulated feed, KELP=fresh *Ecklonia maxima*, ULVA: fresh *Ulva lacinulata*. The shaded part of the graph represents the acclimation period before the administration of the experimental feeds..... 61

Figure 30. Box plots comparing the gonad weight (A) and gonad somatic index (GSI) (B) of *Tripneustes gratilla* fed three experimental diets: FF= Formulated feed, KELP=fresh *Ecklonia maxima*, ULVA: fresh *Ulva lacinulata*. 62

Figure 31. Specific growth rates for test diameter, test height and total wet-weight (mean±SE) for the sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla* within the varying feeding frequency and feed volume treatments. . 62

Figure 32. The gonad somatic index (GSI) and gonad wet weight (mean±SE) of *Tripnesutes gratilla* within the varying feeding frequency and feed volume treatments..... 63

Figure 33. (A) Sea urchin tunnel at the South African IMTA Lab; (B, C) juvenile sea urchins stocked into the system; (D,E) baskets holding sea urchins that are measured on a weekly basis; (F) sea urchin gonads/product. ©UCT/DFFE 64

Figure 34. *Tripneustes gratilla* (A) mean±SEM diameter in mm and (B) mean±SEM individual weights in g over the 8-month experimental period, as well as the (C) mean±SEM gonad somatic index (GS) of urchins during the gonad enhancement phase (month 6, 7 and 8) of the trial. Dietary treatments included: 1) Fresh *Ulva* (FU) from zero to six months (Somatic growth phase), then finished off with pellets from feed manufacturer 1 from month 6 onwards [FU-20UF1]; 2) Fresh *Ulva* (FU) from zero to six months, then finished off with pellets (20U feed from feed manufacturer 2) from month six onwards [FU-20UF2]; 3) Mixed feeding regime of FU and 20UF1 over the entire production cycle [20UF1]; 4) Mixed feeding regime of FU and 20UM over the entire production cycle [20UF2]; and 5) Mixed feeding regime of FU and AquaVitae formulated feed over the entire production cycle [M-AVF3]. The shaded portion of the graph represents the change in diet within the feeding regimes. . 65

Figure 35. The effect of various feeds and feeding regimes on the diameter (A) and mass (B) specific growth rate of *Tripneustes gratilla* over the 8-month experimental period. Dietary treatments included: 1) Fresh *Ulva* (FU) from zero to six months (Somatic growth phase), then finished off with pellets from feed manufacturer 1 from month 6 onwards [FU-20UF1]; 2) Fresh *Ulva* (FU) from zero to

six months, then finished off with pellets (20U feed from feed manufacturer 2) from month six onwards [FU-20UF2]; 3) Mixed feeding regime of FU and 20UF1 over the entire production cycle [20UF1]; 4) Mixed feeding regime of FU and 20UM over the entire production cycle [20UF2]; and 5) Mixed feeding regime of FU and AquaVitae formulated feed over the entire production cycle [M-AVF3]..... 66

Figure 36. Experimental design for first optimisation trial for the use of faecal matter from the Cape sea urchin *Parechinus angulosus* as feed for newly depleted juvenile abalone, which was conducted at the Marine Research Aquarium in Sea Point. 75

Figure 37. Experimental design for second optimisation trial for the use of faecal matter from the Cape sea urchin *Parechinus angulosus* as feed for newly depleted juvenile abalone, which was conducted on Buffeljags Abalone Farm. 77

Figure 38. Experimental design for large-scale trial for the use of faecal matter from the Cape sea urchin *Parechinus angulosus* as feed for newly depleted juvenile abalone, which was conducted on Buffeljags Abalone Farm. 78

Figure 39. Juvenile abalone (A) shell length (mm) and (B) cumulative shell length specific growth rate (% growth per day) across dietary treatments. AF: abalone fed formulated feed (control); AUB: abalone under urchins that were kept in baskets; AUBF: abalone that were supplemented with formulated feed and held under urchins in baskets; AU: abalone in direct contact with urchins. 80

Figure 40. Juvenile abalone (A) shell length (mm) and (B) cumulative shell length specific growth rate (% growth per day) across dietary treatments. AF: abalone fed formulated feed and diatoms (control); AUBF: abalone that were supplemented with formulated feed, diatoms and sea urchin faeces from urchin held in baskets above them. 81

Figure 41. Average juvenile abalone shell length (cm) over a duration of 8 weeks across abalone fed only diatoms, a formulated feed, *Ulva* and *Gracilaria* (control, n=300 per time point) and abalone fed diatoms, a formulated feed, *Ulva* and *Gracilaria* while being supplemented with sea urchin faeces (n=300 per time point), with an additional two measurement points after the conclusion of the feeding trial at 16- and 26-weeks. 82

Figure 42. Average juvenile abalone survival over the 8-week trial period across abalone fed only diatoms, a formulated feed, *Ulva* and *Gracilaria* (control, n=300 per time point) and abalone fed diatoms, a formulated feed, *Ulva* and *Gracilaria* while being supplemented with sea urchin faeces (n=300 per time point), with an additional survival assessment one week after the conclusion of the feeding trial. 83

Figure 43. Bacterial genera associated with the feeds sampled, the incoming water, the sea urchin intestines, juvenile abalone that received the faecal matter supplement (T1-T2), the juvenile abalone

only fed the mixed feeding regime without faecal matter (C1-C2), as well as the sea urchin and abalone faecal matter. Numbers in sample IDs represent sampling points (months)..... 84

Figure 44. Venn diagram depicting the number of bacterial genera shared across the sea urchin faecal matter (n=3), the juvenile abalone supplemented with faeces (n=9) and juvenile abalone not supplemented with faeces (control; n=9) at the 2-month sampling point. 84

Figure 45. Cape sea urchin average percentage (%) survival over the 24 week feeding trial across dietary treatments (formulated feed, kelp, mixed and *Ulva*) and temperature conditions (ambient and warmed). Letters above bars represent dietary treatment groups that are significantly different to each other based on Dunn’s test with Bonferroni correction. Hashtags above bars indicate the level of significant difference between temperature treatment groups based on Mann-Whitney U tests (#: P<0.05, ##: P<0.01, ###: P<0.001). No letters or hashtags indicate no significant differences. 85

Figure 46. Cape sea urchin specific growth rate (%) per day for body weight (g) across dietary treatments (formulated feed with 16% *Ulva*, kelp, *Ulva lacinulata* and a mixed feeding regime) and temperature treatments (ambient and warmed) over time. Letters above bars represent dietary treatment groups that are significantly different to each other based on ANOVA, followed by Tukey’s, post hoc pairwise comparison test respectively. Stars above bars indicate the level of significant difference between temperature treatment groups (*P<0.05, **P<0.01, ***P<0.001). No letters or stars indicate no significant differences. 86

Figure 47. Cape sea urchin gonad somatic index (GSI; %) across dietary treatments (formulated feed with 16% *Ulva*, kelp, *Ulva lacinulata* and a mixed feeding regime) and temperature treatments (ambient and warmed) over time. Letters above bars represent dietary treatment groups that are significantly different to each other based on ANOVA, followed by Tukey’s, post hoc pairwise comparison test respectively. 87

Table 1. Species cultivated at the site: South African abalone, sea lettuce, collector sea urchin and Cape sea urchin..... 17

Table 2. Summary of optimal value for the various parameters investigated in this study for the commercial cultivation of warm water sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla*. 72

3. Introduction

3.1. ASTRAL

The H2020 project ASTRAL developed new, sustainable, profitable and resilient value chains for integrated multi-trophic aquaculture (IMTA) production within the framework of existing, emerging and potential Atlantic markets. The project gathered four IMTA labs including open-water (Ireland, Scotland), land-based pump-ashore with partial (50%) recirculation (South Africa) and recirculation 'biofloc' land-based (Brazil) systems as well as one prospective IMTA lab (Argentina). The labs focused on a regional challenge-based perspective, including fish, mollusc, echinoderm, crustacean and algae species and the project assessed how to increase circularity using IMTA methods of cultivation. ASTRAL increased circularity by 50-60% compared to monoculture aquaculture and provided a circular business model, boosting revenue diversification for aquaculture producers and increasing profitability by at least 30%. New and improved innovative technologies were developed, including biosensors, sensors, Internet of Things (IoT) and an Artificial Intelligence (AI) data analytics platform was validated at the IMTA labs. Potential environmental and climatic risks for Northern and Southern Atlantic regions were addressed, delivering a monitoring programme and recommendations for Harmful Algal Blooms (HABs), pathogens and microplastics. ASTRAL delivered an ambitious and gender-sensitive human capital development plan (HUCAP) that seeks to improve professional skills and create a highly trained workforce. The project gathered a collaborative ecosystem within the project framework bringing together and connecting industrial partners, SMEs, scientists, policy makers, social representatives and other relevant stakeholders promoting data exchange, knowledge sharing and business opportunities.

3.2. IMTA in land-based partially recirculated systems in South Africa

Several South African commercial aquafarms practice integrated aquaculture. At least five large farms grow *Ulva* in abalone effluent water and feed this back to abalone, thus recycling nutrients sourced from feed and excreted by the animals. This practice has occurred very successfully for over a decade in South Africa and has contributed to the success of the abalone industry — which currently produces approximately 2500 tonnes of abalone per year on around 14 farms². This production represents more than 90% of the value of South African marine aquaculture. Approximately 2500 tonnes of *Ulva* are also grown per annum on South African abalone farms, which is largely used on-farm as feed.

² Department of Forestry, Fisheries and the Environment (DFFE), South Africa, 2022 — Aquaculture yearbook 2022, Status of the Sector, Cape Town, South Africa.

The production of animals in systems integrated with seaweeds has numerous benefits. Seaweeds are an excellent source of minerals, vitamins, complex polysaccharides and other bioactive compounds. When used as a supplementary feed or a feed additive, research has shown that *Ulva* enhances the chemosensory properties of formulated feeds, significantly improves feed conversion ratio (FCR), feed consumption and digestible protein and energy intake by both abalone and sea urchins^{3,4,5,6}. Due to the existing pigments in the seaweed, e.g., carotenoids, such as β -carotene, studies have demonstrated that dietary supplementation with *Ulva* improves the colour and marketable properties of urchin gonads³. *Ulva* also has additional benefits in that it reduces nutrient release from farms into the sea, reduces reliance on harvesting natural seaweeds and reduces dependence on the use of protein rich formulated feeds⁷. The bioremediation ability of the seaweed can reduce pumping costs by partial recirculation of water to abalone and urchins from seaweed tanks. This recirculation system has also been successfully used in South Africa to protect abalone farms from Harmful Algal Blooms ('red tides'), where the recirculation rate from the *Ulva* raceways was increased for a short period under HAB conditions. Collectively, this integrated method of cultivating abalone and sea urchin results in the production of high value seafood species, as well as valuable by-products (derived from the seaweeds), in an economically and environmentally sustainable manner.

Despite these advantages, Buffeljags and Diamond Coast Abalone, both subsidiaries of the Viking Aquaculture group, and are the only two farms in South Africa currently operating land-based partially recirculated IMTA systems. The paucity of information on the physical and chemical parameters of these systems, as well as biosecurity concerns associated with water recirculation and use of effluent-grown *Ulva* as a feed or functional feed ingredient has prevented wider adoption of this technology on other abalone farms in South Africa and abroad. These were some of the key factors for undertaking the research described in this deliverable.

³ Cyrus M.D., Bolton J.J., Macey B.M., De Wet L., 2014. The development of a formulated feed containing *Ulva* (Chlorophyta) to promote rapid growth and enhanced production of high quality roe in the sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla* (Linnaeus). *Aquaculture Research* 45:159-176.

⁴ Cyrus M.D., Bolton J.J., Scholtz R., Macey B.M., 2015. The advantages of *Ulva* (Chlorophyta) as an additive in sea urchin formulated feeds: effects on palatability, consumption and digestibility. *Aquaculture Nutrition*. 21:578-591.

⁵ Naidoo K., Maneveldt G., Ruck K., Bolton J.J. 2006. A comparison of various seaweed-based diets and formulated feed on growth rate of abalone in a land-based aquaculture system. *Journal of Applied Phycology* 18:437-443.

⁶ Kemp J.O.G., Britz P.J., Agüero P.H.T., 2015. The effect of macroalgal, formulated and combination diets on growth, survival and feed utilisation in the red abalone *Haliotis rufescens*. *Aquaculture* 448:306-314.

⁷ Bolton J.J., Robertson-Andersson D.V., Shuuluka D., Kandjengo L., 2009. Growing *Ulva* (Chlorophyta) in integrated systems as a commercial crop for abalone feed in South Africa: a SWOT analysis. *Journal of Applied Phycology* 21:575-583.

3.3. IMTA Lab South Africa – Land-based pump ashore system

3.3.1. Site Description

IMTA Lab South Africa is based at Buffeljags Abalone farm, which produces approximately 450 tons of the abalone *Haliotis midae* and 600 tons of the green seaweed *Ulva lacunculata* annually. The farm is one of the first large commercial abalone farms in South Africa to consistently recirculate 50% of their seawater by making use of the bioremediation capacity of *Ulva*.

To augment biosecurity concerns, Buffeljags Abalone has been specifically designed to consist of modular units. There are seven modular abalone-*Ulva* IMTA systems at the farm, referred to as platforms, which are each composed of four clusters that each consist of one D-ended *Ulva* paddle-raceway and 42 abalone raceway tanks (6 rows each made of 7 abalone raceway tanks) (Figure 2). All the effluent water leaving the abalone tanks is bioremediated by the *Ulva* in the adjacent paddle-raceway before being mixed with 50% fresh seawater in the sump. The sump is also equipped with a protein skimmer to remove further waste and dissolved organic nutrients from the bioremediated seawater before it is returned to the abalone raceways. The clusters do not share water, equipment and other fomites, and various biosecurity measures are implemented to minimize the risk(s) of introducing an infectious disease and spreading it to the animals at a facility and/or between clusters.

Figure 2. Land-based pump ashore IMTA system to produce abalone (*Haliotis midae*) and seaweed (*Ulva lacunculata*) at Buffeljags Abalone Farm. (A) Aerial photograph of the modular abalone-*Ulva* IMTA (©Viking Aquaculture). (B) Schematic of the IMTA process in a single abalone-*Ulva* cluster (©Brett Macey).

The species at the South African IMTA Lab (Table 1; Figure 3) are categorised as: fed, extractive, or novel species.

1. **Fed species:** Feed is inputted to the system for the South African abalone (*Haliotis midae*), the warm water sea urchin (*Tripneustes gratilla*), and the Cape sea urchin (*Parechinus angulosus*). As a result, the animals release waste/nutrients into the water that is used as a nutrient source for the extractive seaweed species and/or other species grown in the integrated system.
2. **Extractive species:** Dissolved 'waste' is extracted by the seaweed *Ulva lacinulata* that is grown in D-ended paddle raceway systems adjacent to the abalone and urchin systems. The seaweed absorbs the dissolved inorganic nitrogen (DIN), which allows for partial to full water recirculation, and the *Ulva* grown in the system serves as a supplementary feed for the abalone and urchins.
3. **Novel species:** Warm water 'tropical' sea urchin, *Tripneustes gratilla*, are fed with seaweed grown in the IMTA process, thus enhancing circularity; and the temperate sea urchin, *Parechinus angulosus*, are fed with seaweeds and their faecal material is used as supplementary feed/probiotic for juvenile abalone, *Haliotis midae*, improving abalone growth/health and enhancing circularity.

Table 1. Species cultivated at the site: South African abalone, sea lettuce, collector sea urchin and Cape sea urchin.

<u>Common name</u>	<u>Latin name</u>	<u>Role in IMTA</u>
Abalone	<i>Haliotis midae</i>	Fed species
Sea lettuce	<i>Ulva lacinulata</i>	Extractive species
Collector sea urchin	<i>Tripneustes gratilla</i>	Fed, novel species
Cape sea urchin	<i>Parechinus angulosus</i>	Fed, novel species

Figure 3. Species cultivated at the South African IMTA Lab. (A) South African abalone, *Haliotis midae* (© John Bolton); (B) sea lettuce, *Ulva lacunculata* (© Mark Cyrus); (C) collector sea urchin, *Tripneustes gratilla* (© Bas de Vos); and (D) Cape urchin, *Parechinus angulosus* (© Marissa Brink-Hull).

3.3.2. Cultivation Environment

The land-based pump ashore IMTA production at Buffeljags Abalone (<https://www.vikingaquaculture.co.za/abalone/farming/>), is located on a pristine stretch of coastline near the remote settlement of Buffeljags on the Cape south coast (34°45'14.7" S 19°36'51.9" E) of South Africa (Figure 4).

The Cape south coast has a temperate climate that is characterised by long warm and dry summers and cool and wet, but relatively short winters. The average annual air temperature in the region is 17°C and is at its highest in January/February and lowest in July.

Over the course of the year, the air temperature typically varies from 8.8°C to 24.5°C and is rarely below 5°C or above 29°C⁸. All seawater to produce the species at IMTA lab South Africa is pumped directly from the Atlantic Ocean, via an intake pipe located amongst the kelp beds directly in front of the farm. The mean water temperature for the coastal seawater in this area is 15.6°C, with an absolute minimum of 9°C to an absolute maximum of 23.5°C (20-year average). Salinity at this site is ca. 35 psu.

Figure 4. Location of IMTA Lab South Africa — Buffeljags Abalone Farm (© Brett Macey).

4. IMTA species

4.1 Abalone *Haliotis midae* integrated with *Ulva lacinulata*

4.1.1 Introduction

As described, Buffeljags Abalone farm was designed and runs continually at 50% recirculation. This is enabled by passing the abalone effluent through seaweed (*Ulva*) paddle raceways to remove excess dissolved ammonia nitrogen released by the abalone. If the free ammonia nitrogen (FAN) component reaches above certain levels (0.01 mg.L⁻¹), this becomes toxic for the abalone. Thus, removal of the bulk of the dissolved ammonia by the *Ulva* and mixing of the bioremediated effluent in the sump with

⁸ <https://weatherspark.com/y/82961/Average-Weather-in-Cape-Town-South-Africa-Year-Round>

equal amounts of fresh seawater, has enabled the farm to run successfully and abalone to remain healthy and grow at commercially acceptable rates for a decade.

Initial studies on using *Ulva* to enable seawater recirculation on South African abalone farms used lower recirculation rates. For example, the initial trials of Robertson-Andersson et al.⁹, producing data from which the first commercial system was built¹⁰, used 25% recirculation.

The aim of the current trial was to monitor changes in pH, temperature, dissolved oxygen, and nutrients (PO₄, NO₂, NO₃, NH₄: total ammonia nitrogen (TAN) and free ammonia nitrogen (FAN)) in the integrated abalone-*Ulva* systems at Buffeljags Abalone farm operating at:

1. Fifty percent (50%) recirculation over a one-month period, which is the standard operating procedure on the farm and serves as the control in this study;
2. Seventy-five percent (75%) recirculation for one month to investigate if abalone could successfully be grown over an extended period at a higher recirculation rate than current; and
3. One hundred percent (100%) recirculation, for a brief period. The aim of this was to see if the entire system could be closed off to contact with the sea, particularly in potential cases of Harmful Algal Blooms^{7,11}. In initial trials¹² this had been carried out for 3 days without adverse effects on the system or the animals. This was run while closely monitoring the environmental parameters (particularly the oxygen and toxic ammonia components) as well as the animals and was terminated when levels of FAN were considered too high.

Microorganisms play various roles in aquaculture systems, including dissolved organic matter decomposition, fermentation, nitrification, nutrient cycling and protection against pathogenic microorganisms. Enteric bacteria, which are established early in invertebrate life cycles, are capable of the synthesis of essential amino acids, provisioning of digestive enzymes, improvement of digestive efficiency, nitrogen metabolism, and provide access to essential micronutrients. The bacterial communities in aquaculture environments are likely influenced by feeds and environmental factors

⁹ Robertson-Andersson D.V., Potgieter M., Hansen J., Bolton J.J., Troell M., Anderson R.J., et al., 2008. Integrated seaweed cultivation on an abalone farm in South Africa. *Journal of Applied Phycology* 20: 579-595.

¹⁰ Bolton J.J., Robertson-Andersson D.V., Shuuluka D., Kandjengo L., 2009. Growing *Ulva* (Chlorophyta) in integrated systems as a commercial crop for abalone feed in South Africa: a SWOT analysis. *Journal of Applied Phycology* 21: 575-583.

¹¹ Pitcher G.C., Foord C.J., Macey B.M., Mansfield L., Mouton A., et al., 2019. Devastating farmed abalone mortalities attributed to yessotoxin-producing dinoflagellates. *Harmful Algae* 81:30-41.

¹² De Prisco J.A., 2020. An investigation of some key physio-chemical water quality parameters of an Integrated Multi-Trophic Aquaculture (IMTA) system operating recirculation methodology in the Western Cape of South Africa. MSc dissertation, University of Cape Town, South Africa.

but could also be influenced by the changing conditions during grow-out phases and may be impacted by water recirculation in IMTA systems.

The paucity of information on the microbiome of these systems has prevented wider adoption of IMTA as there are biosecurity concerns associated with water recirculation and the use of effluent grown *Ulva* as a feed for abalone, even though dietary seaweed supplementation has previously been shown to improve feed consumption, growth and health of cultured abalone^{13,14,15,16}.

Despite the benefits of IMTA, biosecurity concerns associated with water recirculation and use of effluent-grown *Ulva* as feed are preventing wider adoption of this technology on abalone farms in South Africa. To better understand potential benefits and risks associated with IMTA, the IMTA lab South Africa characterized the microbiome associated with seawater, *Ulva* and abalone from integrated abalone-*Ulva* systems operating at 50% recirculation (default operation) (Trial 2), at increasing recirculation rates as described above (Trial 3), as well as for abalone that were fed formulated feeds with *Ulva* or *Ulva*-component inclusion (Trial 4). Molecular barcoding studies were also carried out to clarify the species of *Ulva* grown on abalone farms in South Africa, as well as investigations to ascertain the temperature tolerances of local species with respect to the spectrum of seawater temperature regimes in the various regions where farms occur.

4.1.2 Trial Methodology

Trial 1 – Monitoring the physical and chemical parameters of the abalone-Ulva IMTA system

These environmental parameters were studied simultaneously with the collection of the microbiome data in the system (Trial 3 below). Three abalone-*Ulva* clusters (Figure 2: Cluster 2.1 = platform 2 cluster 1; Cluster 2.2 = platform 2 cluster 2; and Cluster 3.1 = platform 3 cluster 1) at Buffeljags abalone were used for this study, each containing approximately 15 tons of abalone *Haliotis midae* and 1.5 tons of the green seaweed *Ulva lacunculata*.

The 50% recirculation trial started on the 21st of July 2021 and ran for one month. During this period, pH and temperature data were monitored every day continuously on every hour using Hobo pH/temp data loggers in the *Ulva* raceway of each cluster for two weeks, before being placed in an abalone

¹³ Naidoo K., Maneveldt G., Ruck K., Bolton J.J. 2006. A comparison of various seaweed-based diets and formulated feed on growth rate of abalone in a land-based aquaculture system. *Journal of Applied Phycology* 18:437-443.

¹⁴ Mulvaney W.J., Winberg P.C., Adams L., 2013. Comparison of macroalgal (*Ulva* and *Grateloupia* spp.) and formulated terrestrial feed on the growth and condition of juvenile abalone. *Journal of Applied Phycology*. 25:815-824.

¹⁵ Kemp J.O.G., Britz P.J., Agüero P.H.T., 2015. The effect of macroalgal, formulated and combination diets on growth, survival and feed utilisation in the red abalone *Haliotis rufescens*. *Aquaculture* 448:306-314.

¹⁶ Bansemmer M.S., Qin J.G., Harris J.O., Duong D.N., Hai T., Howarth G.S., et al., 2016. Growth and feed utilisation of greenlip abalone (*Haliotis laevis*) fed nutrient enriched macroalgae. *Aquaculture* 452:62-68.

raceway within each cluster for the remaining two weeks of the 50% (normal operation) trial. Samples for nutrient (phosphate, nitrate, nitrite, and ammonia) analysis were collected once a week from each cluster in the morning (08h00) and afternoon (13h00), to monitor daily changes in concentrations. These times were chosen to coincide with the high metabolic activity of the abalone at night, and expected high nutrient levels early in the morning, and peak photosynthetic activity of *Ulva* mid-day. Water samples were collected in 50 mL sterile centrifuge tubes from a pipe exiting the abalone raceways (abalone effluent water). Following collection, samples were immediately frozen until needed for analysis.

The 75% recirculation trial started on the 25th of August 2021, and also ran for a period of one month. The sampling of this system was the same as for the 50% system. The 100% trial commenced on the 8th of November 2021 and the systems were maintained at full recirculation for ca. 3 days. During this trial, pH and temperature data were only monitored in the abalone raceways to ensure that conditions did not exceed dangerous levels that would influence abalone behaviour or health. The Hobo pH/temp data loggers were placed near the inlets of each abalone raceway within each cluster. Additional measurements of pH, dissolved oxygen, salinity, and temperature were recorded once every two hours, whereas nutrients were recorded once every four hours on the systems during this time to ensure optimal water quality and welfare for animals. Samples were also taken following the bioremediation by the *Ulva*, which was collected from the water returning to the abalone raceways from the *Ulva* paddle raceway. OxyGuard Handy Polaris hand-held pH, temperature and DO meters were utilised for measuring these parameters. Total ammonia nitrogen (TAN) was recorded *in situ* using a Lovibond® MD 600 Photometer and the recorded TAN, pH, temperature, and salinity values were used to calculate the free un-ionized ammonia (FAN) using a free ammonia calculator¹⁷. In addition to the *in situ* nutrient measurement, water samples were collected simultaneously from each system once every 4 hours for nutrient measurements at the DFFE laboratories in Sea Point (Cape Town), to provide validation of the readings recorded *in situ* on the farm.

Nutrients were measured at the chemistry laboratory in the DFFE from frozen samples (PO₄, NO₂, NO₃, and NH₄). Total Ammonia Nitrogen (TAN) was calculated using a modified version of the spectrophotometric Grasshoff method¹⁸, which uses a calibrated indophenol blue spectrophotometric technique. To test the efficacy of the *Ulva* raceway as a biofilter, 100% recirculation measurements were used. Samples were taken entering and leaving the *Ulva* raceway. Additionally, the change between the concentrations going into and out of the abalone raceway, for 50% and 100%

¹⁷ Arain H.M., 2022. Aquarium Calculators [online] Available at: <https://www.hamzasreef.com/Contents/Calculators/>.

¹⁸ Grasshoff K., Kremling K., Ehrhardt M., 1999. Methods of seawater analysis. 3rd Edition, Wiley, Verlag Chemie Weinheim, New York, pp. 419.

recirculation, were compared to see the effects of recirculation rate on maximum nutrient levels in the system. An important component of the nutrient analysis are the total ammonia nitrogen (TAN) and the free ammonia nitrogen (FAN) components. These are related and linked to pH and temperature; however, FAN is of particular importance in an aquaculture system due to its toxicity. TAN and FAN are plotted over 72 hours for 50% and 75% recirculation to monitor daily fluctuation.

Dissolved oxygen (DO) was measured for the 50% control and the 100% recirculation rate to see the daily trends, as well as to detect whether the critical DO level (7 mg.L^{-1}) for abalone health was exceeded.

Trial 2 – Microbiome studies of the abalone-Ulva IMTA system at Buffeljags Abalone Farm

For the partially recirculating (50% recirculation) land-based system in South Africa, *Ulva* and seawater samples were collected from two types of *Ulva* paddle-raceway systems at Buffeljags Abalone Farm. One system consisted of tanks that received seawater directly from the adjacent coastline, hereafter referred to as the seawater (SW) or non-IMTA *Ulva* paddle-raceway system. The other systems comprised paddle-raceways receiving abalone effluent water, with 50% recirculation between the abalone and *Ulva* raceways, referred to as abalone effluent water (AEW) or IMTA paddle-raceway systems. *Ulva* samples were collected from within each paddle-raceway, whereas the water samples were collected at the inlet (representative of effluent water from the abalone tanks) and outlet (representative of water bio-remediated by *Ulva*) of each *Ulva* paddle-raceway. One SW *Ulva* paddle-raceway (only one exists on the farm) and 4 AEW *Ulva* paddle-raceways were sampled in autumn ($n = 1$), winter ($n = 1$), spring ($n = 1$) and summer ($n = 1$). Water samples (500 mL, in triplicate) were filtered through $0.22 \mu\text{m}$ filter membranes to concentrate microbial cells. A total of 64 samples (including controls) were collected and pre-processed prior to DNA extractions.

Microbial DNA was isolated using a QIAamp® DNA Micro Kit (Qiagen, Cat. No. 56304) following the manufacturer's instructions. Sequencing of the hyper-variable V4 region (360-370 basepairs) was carried out with the following forward and reverse primers: V4 – 515F/806R (5'TCGTCGGCAGCGTCAGATGTGTATAAGAGACAGGTGYCAGCMGCCGCGGTAA/5'GTCTCGTGGGCTCGGAGATGTGTATAAGAGACAGGGGACTACNVGGGTWTCTAAT). The underlined sequences are the adaptor overhang nucleotide sequences used in the Illumina 16S metagenomics workflow. PCR products were normalized to equal concentrations and sequenced using an Illumina® MiSeq sequencing instrument. Sequencing was carried out at the Centre for Proteomic and Genomic Research (CPGR) in South Africa¹⁹ using a MiSeq Reagent v2 Kit (500 cycles) with 2×250 paired end reads.

¹⁹ <https://www.cpgr.org.za/>

Demultiplexed paired-end FASTQ files were imported into the Quantitative Insights into Microbial Ecology 2 program (QIIME2- 2020.11). The Divisive Amplicon Denoising Algorithm 2 (DADA2) software package²⁰ in QIIME2, was used to quality filter, trim, de-noise, and merge reads. Taxonomy was assigned to amplicon sequence variants (ASVs) using the SILVA database²¹. The raw sequence processing was performed using facilities provided by the University of Cape Town's ICTS High Performance Computing team (hpc.uct.ac.za). All data analysis was conducted in MicrobiomeAnalyst²² using the R packages *vegan*²³ and *phyloseq*²⁴. Briefly, a marginally filtered dataset, based on ASVs, was used to calculate and estimate overall taxonomic abundance and diversity metrics. Uneven sequencing depth, under-sampling, and data sparsity were all corrected for using the relative log expression (RLE) transformation²⁵, prior to conducting between sample differential abundance assessments (DESeq2)²⁶.

Trial 3 – Microbiome of the abalone-Ulva IMTA at Buffeljags abalone with increasing recirculation rates (50% to 75% to 100%).

Refer to 'Trial 1' above for details of the experimental system at Buffeljags abalone and 'Trial 2' for details on where samples were collected and how they were processed and analysed for the bacterial microbiome. Briefly, the abalone-*Ulva* IMTA was run at a recirculation rate of 50% (baseline — as this is how the farm normally operates) across three clusters on the abalone-*Ulva* integrated farm (Figure 2) for a month and samples (water from inlets, water from outlets, *Ulva*, abalone fringe, abalone intestine and sediment) were collected at the start and end of the month for microbiome assessments. The recirculation rate in the IMTA was then increased to 75% in each cluster for a month and samples were collected as before at the end of the month for microbiome assessments. Finally, the recirculation rate of the IMTA was increased to 100% for ca. 4 days and samples were collected as before for microbiome assessments at the end of the 100% recirculation trial.

Samples of seawater (500 mL, in triplicate) were collected from the inlet (representative of effluent water from the abalone tanks) and outlet (representative of water bio-remediated by *Ulva*) of each

²⁰ Callahan B.J., McMurdie P.J., Rosen M.J., Han A.W., Johnson A.J.A., Holmes S.P., 2016. DADA2: High-resolution sample inference from Illumina amplicon data. *Nature Methods* 13:581-583.

²¹ Quast C., Pruesse E., Yilmaz P., Gerken J., Schweer T., Yarza P., et al., 2013. The SILVA ribosomal RNA gene database project: Improved data processing and web-based tools. *Nucleic Acid Research* 41:D590-D596.

²² Dhariwal A., Chong J., Habib S., King I.L., Agellon L.B., Xia J., 2017. MicrobiomeAnalyst: a web-based tool for comprehensive statistical, visual and meta-analysis of microbiome data. *Nucleic Acid Research* 45:180-188.

²³ Dixon P., 2003. VEGAN, a package of R functions for community ecology. *Journal of Vegetative Science* 14:927-930.

²⁴ McMurdie P.J., Holmes S., 2013. Phyloseq: an R package for reproducible interactive analysis and graphics of microbiome census data. *PLoS ONE* 8:e61217.

²⁵ Hawinkel S., 2015. Evaluation of normalization and analysis methods for microbiome data. Unpublished M.Sc, Gent University, Belgium.

²⁶ Love M.I., Huber W., Anders S., 2014. Moderated estimation of fold change and dispersion for RNA-seq data with DESeq2. *Genome Biology* 15:550.

Ulva paddle-raceway in three clusters — receiving abalone effluent water from adjacent abalone raceways. All samples were collected in triplicate. Seawater samples were filtered through 0.22- μ m-pore-size filter membranes (47-mm diameter, Millipore Corp., Bedford, Mass.) to concentrate bacteria, fungi and oomycetes, where after microbial cells were isolated from the filters, concentrated and resuspended in DNA/RNA shield (Zymo) and stored at -80°C . *Ulva* samples, along with abalone fringe (25-50 mg), abalone intestines (25-50 mg) and sediment samples (25 mg) (in triplicate) were also collected from each cluster at the same time. These samples were fixed in DNA/RNA Shield (Zymo) and stored at -80°C . DNA from samples was extracted with ZymoBIOMICS DNA Miniprep kit (Zymo Research, Irvine, Canada), following the manufacturer's instructions. DNA quantification was performed with Qubit (Invitrogen). Sequencing of the variable region V4 was performed with the following forward and reverse primers: V4 – 515F/806R- using 16sRNA metagenomics. A similar data processing workflow as described in Trial 2 was used with one additional R package *microeco*²⁷ used for analysis.

Trial 4 – Gut microbiome of cultured abalone, Haliotis midae, fed various diets

A controlled laboratory trial at the Marine Research Aquarium (MRA) in Sea Point was conducted to test the effects of specific components of *Ulva* on abalone (20-30g) growth, physiology and gut microbiome. Iso-nitrogenous diets consisting of dried *Ulva* (10% w/w; AB10U), Ulvan (1% w/w; AB1U), and glucuronic acid (0.1% w/w; AB0.1U) were formulated. Feed conversion ratio (FCR), specific growth rate (SGR), tissue glycogen, and gut microbiome was assessed on days 0, 105 and 215 and compared to abalone fed a formulated diet (diet AB), fresh *Ulva* (FU), or a combination of the latter (ABFU) for seven months. Dry feeds were administered at 6 - 7 g per tank three times a week for three months, which amounts to a feeding rate of 0.34 - 0.40% combined abalone body weight per tank per day. After the first three months, feed amounts were adjusted to 7 - 8 g per tank three times a week to account for the growth of the abalone. The bacterial microbiome was characterised by using a QIAamp Fast DNA Stool Mini Kit (Cat. No. 51604) to extract the DNA of microorganisms in the intestinal tract of $n = 5$ abalone per diet, and sequencing the V3-4 hyper-variable region of the 16S rRNA gene using an Illumina MiSeq platform at the University of the Western Cape (UWC). Raw sequence data assessed as described in Section 6.1.2, Trial 2. Taxonomic abundance at different hierarchical levels were assessed, bacterial diversity within- and between samples was evaluated and functional differences between gut microbiomes of animals fed different diets were assessed.

Trial 5 – Identity, temperature tolerance and fertility of farmed Ulva lacinulata

²⁷ Liu C., Cui Y., Li X., Yao M., 2021. *Microeco*: an R package for data mining in microbial community ecology. *FEMS Microbiology Ecology* 97:fiaa255.

A molecular barcoding study of the *Ulva* grown on 5 farms over the complete geographical range of abalone cultivation in South Africa was conducted^{28,29}, including samples from the seashore around a cluster of abalone farms, and available specimens of apparently similar local species in nature. The molecular markers employed for this study were the chloroplast-encoded Ribulose-1,5-bisphosphate carboxylase oxygenase (rbcl), the Internal Transcribed Spacer (ITS) of the nuclear ribosomal DNA, and the chloroplast elongation factor tufA.

A laboratory study comparing growth of farmed *Ulva lacunculata* with that of specimens of two similar, bladed (foliose) *Ulva* species from the warm temperate south coast of South Africa was conducted³⁰ to add to existing data on temperature tolerances of local *Ulva*. The main aim was to see which species could grow well at the higher temperature needed to grow *Tripneustes gratilla*. Three temperatures were tested (15, 20 and 25°C) and fertility of the different species was also monitored during this two-week study.

4.1.3 Results

Trial 1 – Monitoring the physical and chemical parameters of the abalone-Ulva IMTA system

Temperature and pH

Figure 5A shows the daily fluctuations in temperature over one month for the 50% (21/07/21 - 24/08/21) and 75% (24/08/21 - 27/09/21) recirculation trials. The best fit line to this trend shows a higher temperature gradient for the 75% recirculation trial compared with the 50% recirculation trial conducted one month earlier, although this is likely because the 50% recirculation was in late winter and the 75% recirculation in early spring. Figure 5B shows the daily variation of temperature associated with the 50, 75, and 100% recirculation trials over the last three days of each trial. The 75% and 100% recirculation rates yielded higher mean temperatures (15.05°C and 19.70°C respectively) than that of the 50% recirculation rate (14.42°C) (with the temperature (°C) at 50% < 75% < 100%), although again the 100% recirculation trial was later (in early summer). It should, though, be borne in mind that on this coastline seawater temperature regime is controlled to a considerable extent by wind-driven upwelling, providing cooler water in summer. Monthly mean seawater temperatures do

²⁸ Bachoo T., Bolton J.J., Macey B.M., Kandjengo L., Reddy, M.M., 2023. Resolving the identity of commercially cultivated *Ulva* (Ulvaceae, Chlorophyta) in integrated seaweed-abalone aquaculture farms in South Africa. *Journal of Phycology* 59:1272-1283.

²⁹ Bachoo T., 2021. Characterization of *Ulva* (Ulvaceae, Chlorophyta) species cultured in commercial abalone farms in South Africa, and comparison with closely related wild species, using morpho-anatomical and molecular methods. MSc dissertation, University of Cape Town, South Africa.

³⁰ Ramashia T., 2023. *Ulva* in aquaculture: fertility and the search for a warm tolerant culture species. Honours thesis, Department of Biological Sciences, University of Cape Town, South Africa.

not differ greatly between seasons. Twenty year monthly mean average seawater temperature in nearby Hermanus averaged ca. 15°C in winter and ca. 17°C in summer³¹.

Figure 5. Temperature (°C) trend for 50% (21/07/21 – 24/08/21) and 75% (24/08/21 – 27/09/21) recirculation trials (A), accompanied by the daily trends in temperature over the last 72 hours of testing for all recirculation rates. (100% recirculation 08/11/2021 – 10-11/2021) (B).

Figure 6A shows the daily fluctuations in pH over the same period as Figure 5A. Figure 6B shows the daily trends in pH over the last 3 days of each recirculation trial. There is no significant difference in the fluctuation patterns of pH between all the circulation rates, although the peak of 100% recirculation is slightly higher than 50%, while 75% is slightly lower. The 50% recirculation shows significantly lower minimum pH values than the other recirculation rates (6.93 pH units). Controlled mostly by daily rhythms of *Ulva* photosynthesis, pH peaks during the afternoon (12h00 to 16h00) and is lowest at night at peak respiration when the abalone are most active. While there is clear daily variation, it is also important to note that the range of variation is small when looking at the mean pH, which ranges from 7.50 pH units in the 50% recirculation to 7.60 pH units in the 100% recirculation.

³¹ Brand M.J., 2023. *Ulva* as a functional feed: A practical investigation into the effects of *Ulva lacinulata* on the growth, consumption, health and gut microbiota of the farmed abalone *Haliotis midae*. PhD thesis, University of Cape Town, South Africa.

Figure 6. The pH (pH units) trend for the 50% (21/07/21 – 24/08/21) and 75% (24/08/21 – 27/09/21) recirculation trials (A), accompanied by the daily trends in pH over the last 72 hours of testing for all recirculation rates (B).

Nutrients

Figure 7 plots and compares nutrient levels in the morning (8 AM) and the afternoon (1 PM) for the 50% (Figure 7A & B, respectively) and 75% recirculation (Figure 7C & D, respectively). The 50% trial was run for four weeks (21/07/21-11/08/21) and each week three measurements were taken, one from each cluster (clusters 2.1, 2.2, and 3.1), in both the morning (8 AM) and the afternoon (1 PM) on the same day. The 75% trial was run for one month and three days (18/08/21- 20/09/21), where three measurements were taken in each new week, one from each cluster (clusters 2.1, 2.2, and 3.1), during the period, in both the morning (8 AM) and the afternoon (1 PM), on the same day. Both the 50% and the 75% measurements were taken at the outlet of the abalone raceway during the period from 21/07/21- 20/09/21.

Figure 7A and B show the nutrient levels in the morning and afternoon for 50% recirculation. No clear differences between the morning and afternoon nutrient concentrations were observed. The overall trend shows that NO_3 has the highest concentration, followed by NH_4 , PO_4 , and finally NO_2 . Levels of NH_4 were generally within the range 4-10 $\mu\text{M.L}^{-1}$ at both times of day, throughout the trial. The NO_3 levels were in the range 5-8 $\mu\text{M.L}^{-1}$ for most of the trial at 50% recirculation, but rose to 8-10 $\mu\text{M.L}^{-1}$ in the final week. This trend changes with a 75% recirculation rate, where there was a greater amplitude of change in both NO_3 and NH_4 concentrations. Levels of NO_3 were around 10 $\mu\text{M.L}^{-1}$ in the first and last week of the experimental period at 75% recirculation, but 10-15 $\mu\text{M.L}^{-1}$ for the middle weeks of the trial period. The NH_4 levels at 75% recirculation were low (3-6 $\mu\text{M.L}^{-1}$) in the first and last two weeks of the trial, but much higher (20-25 $\mu\text{M.L}^{-1}$) in the second and third week. The most important finding was that NH_4 and NO_3 concentrations in 75% recirculation are overall considerably higher than those in 50% recirculation.

Figure 7. Nutrient concentration ($\mu\text{M}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$) in the morning (A) and the afternoon (B) at 50% recirculation, where each week three measurements, one from each cluster (clusters 2.1, 2.2, and 3.1), were taken from the outlet of the abalone raceway, on the same day, from the 21/07/21-11/08/21, as well as at 75% recirculation in the morning (C) and the afternoon (D) where each new week three measurements, one from each cluster (clusters 2.1, 2.2 and 3.1), were taken from the outlet of the abalone raceway 18/08/21-18/08/21.

Figure 8 shows boxplots comparing 50% and 75% recirculation (Figure 8A), 75% and 100% recirculation (Figure 8B) and 50% and 100% recirculation (Figure 8C). The comparison of 50% and 75% uses the same outlet values as in Figure 7. The 75% and 100% comparisons use a combination of values. The only nutrient data provided for the 75% trial were the same outlet values as those used in Figure 7. The 100% recirculation values use a combination of inlet and outlet values. The comparison of 50% and 100% uses the 50% control values, which are inlet and outlet values to compare against the 100% inlet and outlet values. Higher recirculation rates are generally associated with higher nutrient concentration levels.

Figure 8. Boxplots showing the range of nutrient concentration ($\mu\text{M.L}^{-1}$) for 50% and 75% recirculation (outlet concentrations) (A), 75% (outlet concentrations) and 100% (inlet and outlet concentrations) recirculation (B) and 50% (control inlet and outlet concentrations) and 100% (inlet and outlet concentrations) recirculation (C). The box represents the interquartile range (IQR), the middle line represents the median and the whiskers represent 1.5x IQR or range if less than these values, the points represent outliers.

Nutrient removal

Figure 9 compares the day and night measurements of nutrient concentration ($\mu\text{M.L}^{-1}$) of the 100% recirculation trial. Measurements were taken from each cluster every four hours (2.1, 2.2, and 3.1) and a control cluster (3.2) that was running at 50% recirculation. Figure 9A and C show nutrient levels in the water stream flowing into the abalone raceway from the *Ulva* raceway (bioremediated water), whereas Figure 9B and D look at the nutrient concentration in the water stream flowing out of the abalone raceway and into the *Ulva* raceway (effluent water). Comparing the daytime measurements in Figure 9A and B, PO_4 and NO_2 show little change, but there is, on average, a higher nutrient load going out than going into the abalone raceway with NO_3 and NH_4 . The same pattern is observed in the night-time measurements (Figure 9C and D), where PO_4 and NO_2 remain comparatively constant between the in and out measurements. The NO_3 and NH_4 concentrations appear to be on average slightly higher in the nutrient stream going out of the abalone raceway than going into the abalone raceway. There are also clearly higher maximum nutrient concentrations at night (Figure 9C and D), which up to $66 \mu\text{M.L}^{-1}$, compared to during the day (Figure 9A and B), up to $33 \mu\text{M.L}^{-1}$. There is a clear increase in NH_4 concentrations during the course of the trial.

Figure 9. The 100% recirculation nutrient concentrations ($\mu\text{M}\cdot\text{L}^{-1}$), where measurements were taken from each cluster every four hours (2.1, 2.2, and 3.1), and a control cluster (3.2) that was running at 50% recirculation during the day (8 AM-4 PM) going into the abalone raceway (A) and out of the abalone raceway (B) as well as nutrient concentrations during the night (8 PM to 4 AM) going into (C) and out of (D) the abalone raceway from the 8/11/21 to the 11/11/21.

Comparison of the nutrient reduction between 50% and 100% recirculation

Figure 10 below displays the difference between the nutrient concentrations going into the abalone raceway and the nutrient concentration going out of the abalone raceway. The difference is calculated for each nutrient, for both the 50% and 100% recirculation rates. One can then compare whether there is a difference in the *Ulva* raceway's effectiveness at removing nutrients between the 50% and the 100% recirculation rate. Looking at Figure 9, there is no clear difference in nutrient reduction between the 50% and 100% recirculation rates for any of the measured nutrients.

Figure 10. Boxplot comparing the difference between inlet and outlet nutrient concentrations (µM/l) between 50% and 100% recirculation rates. The box represents the interquartile range (IQR), the middle line represents the median and the whiskers represent 1.5x IQR or range if less than these values, the points represent outliers.

Total Ammonia Nitrogen (TAN) and Free Ammonia Nitrogen (FAN)

TAN and FAN are important parameters because they represent the dissociation of the ammonia within the system, which is crucial to control for abalone health. Figure 11 shows the daily fluctuation of both TAN (Figure 11A) and FAN (Figure 11B), from 8/11/21-11/11/21. These results are from the period of intensive monitoring, where nutrient measurements were taken every 2 hours in the 100% recirculation and the control of 50% recirculation. TAN measurements were only recorded every four hours during this period. FAN is related to TAN; therefore, they show the same pattern of daily variation. The trend shows a peak in TAN and FAN in the early morning (4-8 AM) and a minimum value in the afternoon (12-4 PM). The FAN values similar ranges of values as the TAN values.

Figure 11. Daily variation in TAN (A) and FAN (B) concentrations (mg.L⁻¹) over the period (8/11/21 - 11/11/21) of intensive monitoring where TAN measurements were recorded every four hours in both the 100% recirculation and the 50% control recirculation.

Figure 12 shows the results from the period of nutrient testing for all recirculation rates. Since the trend and values for nutrients were similar between morning and afternoon measurements for the 50% and 75% recirculation rates, data was averaged to allow for better comparisons. The daily average NH_4 concentration was calculated, which was then used to get a daily average TAN and FAN value. The 50% and 75% daily averages are taken from the period where measurements were taken from each cluster once a week in the morning and afternoon of the same day for three clusters (2.1, 2.2, and 2.3). The 100% daily averages are taken from the period where measurements were taken from each cluster every four hours (2.1, 2.2, and 3.1). There is a progressive increase in TAN and FAN concentrations in the 100% recirculation trial. The 75% recirculation shows an initial spike in TAN and FAN concentration levels on 25/08/21, 01/09/21, and 20/09/21, which was removed later in the period. The 50% recirculation TAN and FAN values are clearly the lowest, however, they are also very similar to the TAN and FAN values seen in the 75% recirculation, which doesn't have a spike in concentrations. The 50% recirculation managed to maintain low TAN and FAN concentrations during the period (always below 1 mg.L^{-1}). The 75% recirculation reached maximum levels of $3.2\text{-}3.3 \text{ mg.L}^{-1}$ at times during the trial period, whereas the 100% recirculation reached a maximum level of FAN of 6.17 mg.L^{-1} at the end of the 3-day period.

Figure 12. Daily average FAN and TAN concentrations (mg.L^{-1}) over the period where measurements were taken from each cluster once a week in the morning and afternoon on the same day for three clusters (2.1, 2.2, and 2.3) for both 50% and 75% recirculation. The 100% recirculation are daily averages over four days of continuous testing, where measurements were taken from each cluster (2.1, 2.2, and 3.1) every four hours.

Dissolved Oxygen (DO)

Figure 13 shows the daily trends in dissolved oxygen concentration (mg.L^{-1}) levels from 8/11/21 to 11/11/21, for 50% and 100% recirculation rates. There are generally higher dissolved oxygen levels in 100% recirculation than that in 50% recirculation. There is a diurnal rhythm in DO concentrations over the period of testing with higher values in the daytime, demonstrating the importance of *Ulva* photosynthesis.

Figure 13. Dissolved oxygen concentrations (mg.L^{-1}) measured every two hours during intensive monitoring (8/11/21- 11/11/21) for both 50% and 100% recirculation.

Trial 2 – Microbiome studies of the abalone-Ulva IMTA system at Buffeljags Abalone

A detailed study of microbial diversity across seasons in the abalone-*Ulva* IMTA system at Buffeljags Abalone with 50% re-circulation was completed. Microbiome data was collected and analysed from bacteria, fungi, and oomycetes. High microbiome diversity was observed in all samples, with the highest diversity observed in seawater and lowest on *Ulva*. The three most abundant genera detected in all samples were *Vibrio*, *Pseudoalteromonas*, and genera belonging to the family Rhodobacteraceae (Figure 14). *Vibrio*, *Pseudoalteromonas*, Flavobacteriaceae and Arcobacteraceae were more prevalent in water samples from the IMTA and monoculture systems, whereas *Granulosicoccus* and genera belonging to the family Saprospiraceae were more prevalent on blades of *Ulva* (Figure 14). A higher *Vibrio* abundance was observed for water samples collected in autumn and summer. The relative abundance of specific bacteria (e.g., *Vibrio*, *Pseudoalteromonas*) decreased as the seawater moved from the inlets to the outlets of the *Ulva* paddle-raceway systems.

Further taxonomic abundance profiling revealed the presence of diverse bacterial communities associated with the samples collected from Buffeljags Abalone Farm, with 380 ASVs identified at genus level and some distinct differences between the groups. Bacteria belonging to the genera *Vibrio*, *Pseudoalteromonas* and *Acinetobacter*, and families Flavobacteriaceae, Arcobacteraceae and Rhodobacteraceae were more prevalent in the seawater samples collected from the *Ulva* raceways (inlet and outlets), whereas bacteria belonging to the genera *Granulosicoccus* and *Maribacter*, and families Saprospiraceae and Rhodobacteraceae were more prevalent on the *Ulva* samples growing in the raceways (both IMTA and non-IMTA) (Figure 14). Some of the bacteria found to be associated with *Ulva* in the present study, such as species within the Class gammaproteobacteria (e.g., *Marinobacter* sp.) and Family Rhodobacteraceae (*Roseovarius* sp.).

Figure 14. Relative amplicon sequence variant (ASV) abundance at genus level across the 60 samples from the South African lab. The 30 most abundant ASVs are depicted and the remaining ASVs were grouped as “Others”. Non-IMTA=seawater system; IMTA=abalone effluent water system.

Non-metric multi-dimensional scaling (NMDS) plots revealed that the water and *Ulva* samples are different in terms of beta diversity (Figure 15), with some separation observed for water samples collected from the IMTA (AEW) and non-IMTA (SW) (PERMANOVA; $P < 0.001$). Distinct clustering was also evident for the *Ulva* samples collected from the IMTA and non-IMTA systems, indicative of unique microbial communities associated with the *Ulva* grown in the two systems. The microbiome associated with the inlet and outlet water samples collected from each system showed a degree of overlap, however the bacterial community profile of the outlet samples shifted towards the profile of the *Ulva* samples, supporting that *Ulva* has a modulatory effect on the microbiome as the water moves

from the inlet to the outlet of the paddle raceway systems which was observed in both the IMTA and non-IMTA systems.

Figure 15. Non-metric multidimensional scaling (NMDS), computed from Bray-Curtis distance matrix and grouped by sample (inlet, outlet and *Ulva*) and system type (SW=seawater/non-IMTA system; AEW=abalone effluent water/IMTA system).

Trial 3 – Microbiome of the abalone-Ulva IMTA at Buffeljags abalone with increasing recirculation rates (50% to 75% to 100%)

The Shannon index of the different recirculation rates were investigated to assess bacterial diversity in the system. Shannon index lowers as recirculation rates (50, 75, 100) increases for most of the samples (Figure 16). Water samples from inlet to outlet and *Ulva* samples behaved similarly, decreasing in alpha diversity through time as recirculation rates increase. This supports that *Ulva* has a modulatory effect on the microbiome as the water moves from the inlet to the outlet of the paddle raceway systems. In contrast, abalone intestine samples behave oppositely, having an overall lower Shannon index, pointing at how these samples are not affected in the same way by increasing recirculation (Figure 16). This is likely as the abalone digestive tract is a specialised, niche environment with specific bacterial communities that are integral to digestive functions. Similarly, little difference in within sample diversity was observed in sediment samples over time.

Figure 16. Within-sample diversity represented by the Shannon index across samples collected in this trial (inlet, outlet, sediment, *Ulva* and abalone intestine). Colour indicates sampling timepoints representing the different recirculation rates (50, 75, 100).

A principal component analyses (PCoA) plot revealed that the samples were different in terms of beta (between-sample) diversity, with different degrees of separation observed from obtained samples (Figure 17). Distinct clustering was evident for the abalone intestine samples, indicative of unique microbial communities associated with the abalone gut. The microbiome associated with the inlet and outlet water samples collected from each system showed a degree of overlap. Moreover, *Ulva* samples, although very clustered, had a degree of overlap with inlet and outlet samples, showing that *Ulva* has a unique bacterial community profile, with some shared taxa with the water samples. The sediment samples showed overlap with the water samples, suggesting that the microbiome of the sediment is shaped by the water microbiome in the IMTA system.

Figure 17. Principal Component analyses (PCoA), computed from Bray–Curtis distance matrix and grouped by sample (inlet, outlet, sediment, *Ulva* and abalone intestine) and recirculation (50, 75, 100) at Buffeljags Abalone Farm.

Further taxonomic abundance profiling revealed the presence of diverse bacterial communities associated with the samples collected from Buffeljags Abalone Farm, with 42 ASVs identified at phylum level, 490 at genus level, with some distinct differences between the groups. Most notably, at phylum level, abalone intestine is the one differentiating the most, being composed of mainly Tenericutes, and Fusobacteria. For outlet, inlet, sediments and *Ulva*, the dominant phylum was found to be Proteobacteria (Figure 18). At genus level, *Mycoplasma* and *Psychrilyobacter* were the most prevalent in abalone intestine, which are both found in aquatic organism intestines. On the other hand, genera *Arcobacter*, and *Glaciecola* dominate water and *Ulva* samples.

Figure 18. Bar graph showing the relative (%) amplified sequence variant (ASV) abundance at phylum level across the different sample types (inlet, outlet, sediment, *Ulva* and abalone intestine) and recirculation rates (50, 75 and 100) assessed in this trial. Colours represent the 10 most abundant phyla, where “Others” represents the remaining phyla.

Trial 4 – Gut microbiome of cultured abalone, Haliotis midae, fed formulated diets with Ulva or Ulva-component inclusion

A large extent of similarity was observed for the microbial community profile in abalone fed different diets [IMTA grown *Ulva*, formulated feed, as well as formulated feeds supplemented with dried *Ulva* (10% w/v) or components of *Ulva*, including Ulvan (1% w/w) & glucuronic acid (0,1% w/w)], with the dominant phyla consisting of Fusobacteriota (49%), Proteobacteriota (28%) and Firmicutes (19%). Regardless of dietary treatment, the dominant bacteria consisted of *Psychrilyobacter* (47%), *Vibrio* (21%) and *Mycoplasma* (15%) (Figure 19). However, the relative proportions of these dominant genera differed across diets, with a notable reduction in the opportunistic pathogen *Vibrio* for abalone that were fed diets that included fresh *Ulva* with a corresponding increase in the beneficial *Psychrilyobacter* and *Mycoplasma* genera (Figure 19).

Figure 19. Average relative (%) abundance of bacterial genera observed in the intestines of abalone fed different diets (n = 5 per diet), where the top 30 genera are listed and the remaining genera are denoted as “Others”.

A genus-level Venn diagram (Figure 20) showed many shared bacterial genera across diets, whereas 22 genera were found not to be present in intestines of abalone fed FU, suggesting specific bacteria were selected for and were associated with the digestive tract of abalone fed *Ulva* or components of *Ulva*. A similar modulatory effect of *Ulva* was observed in gut of abalone as for IMTA systems, where various bacterial genera, including members of the genus *Vibrio*, *Shewanella* and *Pseudoalteromonas* were found to be less abundant in the gut of abalone fed the FU-supplemented diets compared to

formulated feed alone. The Venn diagram further supports this observation with a total of 48 genera detected in the FU fed abalone, whereas 70-80 genera were detected in the other dietary treatments that were frequently shared between the respective dietary treatments (Figure 20). Of these genera, *Amylibacter* and an uncultured Vibrionaceae genus were exclusive to the ABFU, AB1U, AB10U and AB0.1G diets.

Figure 20. Venn diagram of the bacterial communities associated with the intestines of abalone fed different diets, showing limited compositional difference between the respective groups with the exception of fresh *Ulva* fed animals having less shared ASVs with the other groups (AB – formulated; ABFU – formulated supplemented with fresh *Ulva*; AB10U – formulated with 10% dried *Ulva* inclusion; AB1U – formulated with 1% *Ulvan* inclusion; AB0.1G – formulated with 0.1% glucuronic acid inclusion; FU – fresh *Ulva*).

Trial 5 – Identity, temperature tolerance and fertility of farmed Ulva lacinulata

Molecular barcoding demonstrated that all the *Ulva* material collected from abalone farms throughout South Africa belongs to a single species, recently renamed *Ulva lacinulata* (Kützing) Wittrock³². From information available so far, this species is rarely found attached on local seashores and was not found in nature around the vicinity of a cluster of abalone farms in Hermanus (where the species is grown in land-based systems). The taxonomy and barcoding of *Ulva* species is currently being reinvestigated globally, and this study is the first to include Southern African species in the new

³² Bachoo T., Bolton J.J., Macey B.M., Kandjengo L. and Reddy M.M., 2023. Resolving the identity of commercially cultivated *Ulva* (Ulvaceae, Chlorophyta) in integrated seaweed-abalone aquaculture farms in South Africa. *Journal of Phycology* 59:1272-1283.

body of knowledge. Several species names have been used for the cultivated material previously, both from a lack of knowledge of the considerable environmentally driven variation in form of this *Ulva* species as well as confusion over nomenclature. The most successful single marker to identify local *Ulva* species proved to be *tufA*.

The temperature experiment looked at growth and fertility of three abundant, local, foliose *Ulva* species in culture: *Ulva lacinulata* (farm material), *Ulva lactuca* (formerly *Ulva fasciata*) and *Ulva uncialis*. *Ulva lacinulata* grew much faster at all temperatures tested than the other two species and remained infertile throughout the experiment. *Ulva lacinulata* grew at similar rates at all temperatures tested, whereas the other two species grew much slower at 25°C than at 15 and 20°C. Long term (8 months) cultivation of *Ulva lacinulata* in the pilot commercial integrated systems with the urchin *Tripneustes gratilla* at Buffeljags (see section 6.2) has also shown that this species grows successfully over long periods at 24°C.

4.1.4 Discussion and Conclusion

There were clear daily rhythms of both temperature and oxygen within the systems, with daytime temperatures resulting in warming, and passage through the seaweed paddle raceways in the system resulting in warming and increased oxygen in the daytime. In the last week of the trials at each recirculation rate, temperature was raised by around 2°C between 50 and 75% recirculation, and a further 2°C between 75 and 100% recirculation. This can be a benefit when ambient temperatures are lower than optimum growth rates for the South African abalone. This occurs throughout the year for farms on the west coast of South Africa/Namibia, and for most of the year at Buffeljags. Temperature could become a problem for Buffeljags with increased recirculation rates in warm water periods/events in the summer.

The pH also had a significant daily pattern of values in these systems, ranging from 8.3 in the day to occasionally as low as 7.0 at night. Overall, there was not a great deal of difference in the pH between the recirculation rates tested. Continuously reduced pH values in intake water, by 0.4 pH units below ambient over the course of a year, have been shown to significantly reduce abalone growth and affect shell shape and strength of *Haliotis midae*³³. However, those studying effects of ocean acidification on shellfish production have generally not examined the effects of large daily fluctuations in pH in a system such as the integrated abalone-*Ulva* system at Buffeljags Abalone (and as is also the case in kelp forests, for example, a natural habitat of the South African abalone). The effect of passing

³³ Lester N., 2021. The interaction of acidification and warming on the South African abalone, *Haliotis midae*, and the potential for mitigation in aquaculture. PhD thesis, University of Cape Town, South Africa.

incoming water through an *Ulva* tank was also tested by Lester (2021). Bio-mitigation of acidified seawater by *Ulva* increased abalone wet weight, GBI, shell length, shell width and shell area in comparison to acidified conditions, although the *Ulva* tank system used was not efficient enough to ameliorate all the effects of pH lowering in the seawater intake of the experimental system.

Nutrient concentrations in the Buffeljags systems were very similar in the morning and afternoon measurements. Although values fluctuated, much higher levels of both ammonia and nitrate were recorded at 75% compared to the standard 50% recirculation. Overall, as might be expected, increased recirculation rates lead to higher concentrations of all nutrients, with a possible exception of phosphorus between 50 and 75% recirculation. Ammonia concentrations (both TAN and FAN) show maximum concentrations in the early morning, an indication of great metabolic activity of the abalone at night, and lower levels in the afternoon. The TAN and FAN levels were consistently low at 50% recirculation ($<1 \text{ mg.L}^{-1}$), variable at 75% recirculation (<1 to $>3 \text{ mg.L}^{-1}$) and high (6 mg.L^{-1}) at the end of the 3-day 100% recirculation trial.

Dissolved oxygen levels were generally higher in the 100% compared to the 50% recirculation system, presumably because more of the water is passed through the seaweed paddle raceway. There was a clear daily pattern in oxygen concentrations in all systems, corresponding to daily rhythms of oxygen release through *Ulva* photosynthesis.

The microbiome studies conducted in the abalone-*Ulva* IMTA system (Trial 2, 3 and 4) showed that the inclusion of *Ulva lacunculata* in IMTA systems results in beneficial changes in the water and farmed species by reducing the presence of opportunistic pathogens. The lower number of unique bacteria associated with *Ulva* in comparison to the seawater sampled in the raceways, supports the notion that *Ulva* only allows specific taxa to colonise the seaweed. *Ulva*-associated bacteria have previously been shown to be beneficial to the growth, morphogenesis and development of *Ulva*³⁴ and could be contributing towards the health of *Ulva* growing vegetatively in the IMTA. When assessing the bacterial community dynamics with increasing recirculation rates, the phylum composition of the samples varies across sampling points, suggesting that recirculation at higher rates has an effect on the microbiome composition. Though the bacterial diversity reduces as the recirculation rate increases, it does not appear to result in an increase in opportunistic bacteria in the various samples collected in this trial, likely as similar patterns were observed in terms of the modulatory effect of *Ulva* on the water microbiome. Notably, this trial (Trial 3) showed that the abalone intestinal microbiome was distinct from the environmental (water and sediment) and *Ulva*-associated microbiome.

³⁴ Weiss A., Costa R., Wichard T., 2017. Morphogenesis of *Ulva mutabilis* (Chlorophyta) induced by *Maribacter* species (Bacteroidetes, Flavobacteriaceae). *Botanica Marina* 60:197-206.

Specific bacterial species are selected for and were associated with the digestive tract of abalone assessed in Trial 4, suggesting the selective nature of the abalone intestinal tract could be contributing to the separation of these samples as observed in Trial 3. Across both trials, abalone had a high abundance of *Psychrilyobacter*, *Mycoplasma* and *Vibrio*, which have all been previously identified in abalone intestines in previous studies^{35,36}. These genera are integral to the digestive processes in the abalone digestive tract, through their roles in fermentation, provisioning of digestive enzymes, and in improving nutrient availability. Including *Ulva* or components of *Ulva* in formulated feeds for farmed abalone further supports the effect of *Ulva* on the microbiome, as a reduction in opportunistic bacteria is observed, with a corresponding increase in beneficial bacteria such as *Psychrilyobacter*.

The commercial use of *Ulva lacinulata* in abalone farms throughout the biogeographical regions of South Africa has been demonstrated by molecular barcoding³⁷ and shown to be due to the high growth rates and particularly wide temperatures tolerances of this species. It is grown successfully from the extreme northwest of South Africa (cool temperate region: seasonal monthly mean temperatures 11.3 to 13.3°C) to the southeast coast (warm temperate region: seasonal monthly mean temperatures 17.9 to 18.6°C). It has also been demonstrated to grow successfully in long-term pilot commercial experiments integrated with the warm water urchin *Tripneustes gratilla* at 24°C³⁸. It remains fertile during long term commercial growth on farms and also in short term laboratory experiments in a wide range of temperatures.

Collectively, the trials conducted in the integrated abalone-*Ulva* IMTA shows that the use of *Ulva* in abalone farming contributes towards the maintenance of system- and animal health through the known reduction of nutrients (nitrogen)^{39,40} and opportunistic microorganisms in the system. The findings from these trials provide critical information on biosecurity of IMTA systems, species health and system health that may promote broader uptake of these more sustainable aquaculture production technologies.

³⁵ Gobet A., Mest L., Perennou M., Dittami S. M., Caralp C., Coulombet C., et al., 2018. Seasonal and algal diet-drive patterns of the digestive microbiota of the European abalone *Haliotis tuberculata*, a generalist marine herbivore. *Microbiome* 6:60.

³⁶ Danckert N.P., Wilson N., Phan-Thien K.-Y., Stone D.A.J., 2021. The intestinal microbiome of Australian abalone, *Haliotis laevigata* and *Haliotis laevigata* × *Haliotis rubra*, over a 1-year period in aquaculture. *Aquaculture* 534:736245.

³⁷ Bachoo T., Bolton J.J., Macey B.M., Kandjengo L. and Reddy M.M., 2023. Resolving the identity of commercially cultivated *Ulva* (Ulvaceae, Chlorophyta) in integrated seaweed-abalone aquaculture farms in South Africa. *Journal of Phycology* 59:1272-1283.

³⁸ Ramashia, T., 2023. *Ulva* in aquaculture: fertility and the search for a warm tolerant culture species. Honours thesis, Department of Biological Sciences, University of Cape Town, South Africa.

³⁹ Robertson-Andersson D.V., Potgieter M., Hansen J., Bolton J.J., Troell M., Anderson R.J., et al., 2008. Integrated seaweed cultivation on an abalone farm in South Africa. *Journal of Applied Phycology* 20:579-595.

⁴⁰ Bolton J.J., Cyrus M.D., Brand M.J., Joubert M., Macey B.M., 2016. Why grow *Ulva*? Its potential role in the future of aquaculture. *Perspectives in Phycology* 3:113-120.

4.2 Urchin *Tripneustes gratilla* integrated with *Ulva lacunculata*

4.2.1 Introduction

South Africa's aquaculture industry is dominated by a limited number of high value species (e.g., abalone, mussels, oysters, trout) and the main aquaculture export in terms of generating foreign income is, overwhelmingly, the supply of abalone to the Asian market. The development of a new highly lucrative export in the form of the sea urchin will help diversify the local aquaculture sector and in so doing help contribute towards key national priorities that include food security, job creation, gross domestic product (GDP), poverty alleviation and rural development. The commercial potential for sea urchin aquaculture (echinoculture) has been identified by a number of countries, including Japan and more recently Australia and South Africa. The rapid growth rate of certain sea urchin species, including the warm water species *Tripneustes gratilla*, their capacity to tolerate high stocking densities, ability to fetch high market prices and the ever-growing demand for urchin products, especially in countries such as Japan that consume more than 80% of all urchin products produced globally, make sea urchins an excellent species for commercialisation.

Several South African commercial abalone farms already practice integrated aquaculture and have done so successfully for more than a decade. However, sea urchins have never been produced commercially in systems integrated with seaweed in South Africa or globally. Due to the success of abalone-*Ulva* IMTA systems in South Africa and the benefits that can be derived from growing *Ulva* in IMTA with a primary crop/species, there is tremendous scope for adapting the existing abalone-*Ulva* technologies for other commercially valuable species. *Ulva* grown in effluent water has several benefits, including use as a feed for primary crops, such as sea urchin and abalone on commercial abalone farms in South Africa — recycling nutrients sourced from feed and excreted by the animals^{41,42}. Nutrition is central to the economics and environmental sustainability of aquaculture. Reduced dependency on fishmeal and imported feeds and the development of novel feeding systems based on enhanced natural productivity (e.g., seaweed culture) offers a cost-effective alternative to costly (can be up to 40% of total production costs for some species), and often non-sustainable, formulated feeds. *Ulva* has additional benefits in that it reduces nutrient release from farms into the sea⁴³, reduces reliance on harvesting natural seaweeds and reduces dependence on the use of protein rich formulated feeds. The bioremediation ability of the seaweed can reduce pumping costs by partial

⁴¹ Bolton J.J., Robertson-Andersson D.V., Shuuluka D., Kandjengo L., 2009. Growing *Ulva* (Chlorophyta) in integrated systems as a commercial crop for abalone feed in South Africa: A SWOT analysis. *Journal of Applied Phycology* 21:575-583.

⁴² Bolton J.J., Cyrus M.D., Brand M.J., Joubert M., Macey B.M., 2016. Why grow *Ulva*? Its potential role in the future of aquaculture. *Perspectives in Phycology* 3:113-120.

⁴³ Neveux N., Bolton J.J., Bruhn A., Roberts D.A., Ras M., 2018. The bioremediation potential of seaweeds: recycling nitrogen, phosphorus, and other waste products. *Blue Biotechnology: Production and Use of Marine Molecules* 1:217-239.

recirculation of water to urchins from seaweed tanks, as is done for abalone⁴⁴. This recirculation system has also been successfully used in South Africa to protect abalone farms from Harmful Algal Blooms ('red tides'), where the recirculation rate from the *Ulva* raceways was increased for a short period under HAB conditions (Nick Loubser, Viking Fishing, pers. comm.). Collectively, the adaptation of this integrated method for cultivating sea urchin will result in the production of a new high value seafood species/ product, as well as valuable by-products, in an economically and environmentally sustainable manner.

Although echinoculture has been practiced in countries such as Japan for many decades, it remains a relatively recent practice that is still in its infancy in most other countries. Internationally, several key areas have been identified that require further research in order to successfully culture urchins on a commercial scale⁴⁵. These include: (1) improving the survival of pluteus larval stage, settlement success and post-settlement survival of larvae; (2) establishment of protocols to allow uniform conditioning of adults prior to harvest; and (3) creation and production of cost-effective diets to optimize somatic and gonadal growth. Researchers from the Department of Forestry, Fisheries and the Environment (DFFE) and University of Cape Town (UCT) have been investigating the culture potential of *Tripneustes* in South Africa since 2008 and have successfully addressed all key areas outlined above to allow for successful commercial scale production of this species^{46, 47, 48, 49, 50, 51}, but technology for upscaling from the research phase to commercial-scale production of larvae and juveniles as well as commercial-scale grow-out of adults requires further developed and optimization.

⁴⁴ Nobre A.M., Robertson-Andersson D., Neori A., Sankar K., 2010. Ecological-economic assessment of aquaculture systems: Comparison between abalone monoculture and integrated multi-trophic aquaculture of abalone and seaweeds. *Aquaculture* 306:116-126.

⁴⁵ Mos B., Cowden K.L., Dworjanyn S.A., 2012. Potential for the commercial culture of the tropical sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla* in Australia. RIRDC Publication No 12/052, RIRDC Project No PRJ-006543.

⁴⁶ Scholtz R., Bolton J.J., Macey B.M., 2013. Effects of different microalgal feeds and their influence on larval development in the white-spined sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla*. *African Journal of Marine Science* 35:25-34.

⁴⁷ Cyrus M.D., Bolton J.J., Macey B.M., De Wet L., 2014. The development of a formulated feed containing *Ulva* (Chlorophyta) to promote rapid growth and enhanced production of high quality roe in the sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla* (Linnaeus). *Aquaculture Research* 45:159-176.

⁴⁸ Cyrus M.D., Bolton J.J., Scholtz R., Macey B.M., 2015. The advantages of *Ulva* (Chlorophyta) as an additive in sea urchin formulated feeds: effects on palatability, consumption and digestibility. *Aquaculture Nutrition*. 21:578-591.

⁴⁹ Cyrus M.D., Bolton J.J., Macey B.M., 2019. The use of stable $\delta^{13}\text{C}$ and $\delta^{15}\text{N}$ isotopes to track the incorporation of *Ulva* and other important dietary ingredients into the gonads of the sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla*. *Aquaculture Nutrition* 26:174-185.

⁵⁰ Onomu, A.J., Vine N.G., Cyrus M.D., Macey B.M., Bolton J.J., 2020. The effect of fresh seaweed and a formulated diet supplemented with seaweed on the growth and gonad quality of the collector sea urchin, *Tripneustes gratilla*, under farm conditions. *Aquaculture Research* 51:4087-4102.

⁵¹ Brink-Hull M., Cyrus M.D., Macey B.M., Rhode C., Hull K.L., Roodt-Wilding R., 2022. Dietary effects on the reproductive performance of the sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla* I: Implications for broodstock conditioning. *Aquaculture* 552.

The research conducted by the ASTRAL IMTA Lab South Africa aimed to take echinoculture from the research phase to the commercial phase and to develop the first pilot commercial echinoculture system, integrated with seaweed, in Southern Africa.

4.2.2 Trial Methodology

*Trial 1 – Optimising basket depth and stocking density for the production of *Tripneustes gratilla**

Basket depth and stocking density are crucial and related factors for successful commercial sea urchin aquaculture, but these factors have not been definitively determined for production of *Tripneustes gratilla*. This trial investigated the effects of varying basket heights (deep 30 cm vs. shallow 15 cm) and stocking densities (4, 6 and 8 kg.m⁻² or 13, 19 and 24% coverage of available basket surface area) on aquacultural production of *T. gratilla*. All trials were conducted at the DFFE Marine Research Aquarium in three 1386 L plastic tanks (140×110×90 cm, length×width×height). The effects of basket depth and feed type on spine loss and consumption were investigated using a 2×3 factorial experimental design with two-treatment levels, basket depth and food type. The three feed types tested (in triplicate) included: formulated feed (pellets) containing 20% dried *Ulva lacinulata*; fresh *U. lacinulata*; and fresh kelp (*Ecklonia maxima*). Both deep (40×15×30.9 cm, L×W×D) and shallow (40×40×15 cm, L×W×D) baskets had an internal surface area of 0.32 m² and stocking density in both treatments was ~6 kg.m⁻². Trials were conducted over 3 days, with baskets cleaned and animals fed *ad libitum* daily. The effect of basket removal on spine loss was also conducted. Effects of stocking density on growth and gonad development of *Tripneustes* fed fresh *Ulva ad libitum* were assessed over 3-months. A separate gonad enhancement trial was conducted for 2-months, where animals were fed formulated feed containing 20% dried *Ulva* (1.5% BW.day⁻¹). Initial stocking density of baskets (40×40×15 cm, L×W×D) for both trials was 4, 6, and 8 kg.m⁻². Urchin growth, gonad development and gonad quality were assessed before and after treatment. Effects of varying stocking densities on urchin parameters (consumption, faecal production, and spine loss) were also assessed.

Trial 2 – Development of a computer vision programme for improved measurement of live sea urchins

To facilitate production of sea urchins in a commercial-scale operation, efficient and precise methods for measuring large numbers of urchins are needed. Current protocols for measuring urchin test (shell) diameter and mass are time-consuming and prone to high measurement error and are therefore not suitable for commercial production. This trial therefore assessed and compared various traditional sea urchin measurement methods with a newly developed computer vision approach developed in this project, to establish a single protocol that would allow for precise and efficient measurement of live urchins in a commercial setting.

Factors affecting the wet mass of urchins (using an electronic balance to the nearest 0.01 g) was determined by assessing the effect of time (30, 60, 90, 120, 180, 300, 480 and 600 s for each urchin) on drip loss, the influence of recent feeding on the wet mass, and precision of measuring the total mass of a group of urchins in a basket versus individual urchins. Urchin test diameter (TD) was manually measured using vernier callipers to the nearest 0.5 mm. Fifty *Tripneustes gratilla* were measured manually by three operators, with operator 1 conducting 3 measurements of the urchins and operator 2 and 3 conducting one measurement each. This allowed for measurement variance to be determined within a single operator and between operators. To ensure robustness/validity of the protocol across urchin species, twenty *Parechinus angulosus* were measured separately three times by a single operator. Each urchin was numbered to ensure the same individuals were compared. Images of each numbered urchin were captured and inputted into the machine vision model, with 10 urchins per image. Specific details regarding the hardware requirements and software development are described by de Vos⁵². Three images were taken of each set of urchins, but the position of numbered urchins was changed randomly between each image. To ensure accessibility of this machine vision program, no specialised equipment was used. Images were acquired using a simple homemade photo box and mobile phone cameras. Specific instructions on the setup can be found in the Read.me file⁵². To check for instrument bias, repeated images of urchins were taken with two different mobile phones, a Samsung A52 and Huawei P30. The program was written in Python3 primarily using the OpenCV library. The machine vision model measured urchin TD by computing the contour of each urchin, using the Canny contour detection algorithm, and the corresponding minimum area bounding rectangle. An HSV filter and basic morphological operations (i.e., blur, erode, dilate) were applied to remove the spines from the measurement area. Settings for the latter used in this analysis are set as defaults; however, these can be adjusted to increase accuracy given various urchin colours and lighting. Statistical analysis was conducted in R. To compare measurement methods, the coefficient of variation (CV) between each measurement was determined within each measurement technique. Each technique was regarded a treatment, and an ANOVA and Tukey tests were applied. To compare the two different phone cameras' effects on measurements, a paired T-test was used. All assumptions were checked and met.

Trial 3 – The effects of acute and chronic exposure to varying salinities (15-40‰) on behaviour, physiology, health (immunity) and growth of Tripneustes gratilla

Sea urchins have been produced globally and potential to develop a local industry has led to the need to determine where these activities can take place. One environmental factor that will greatly

⁵² De Vos B., Cyrus M.D., Macey B.M., Batik T., Bolton J.J., 2023. Combining computer vision and standardised protocols for improved measurement of live sea urchins for research and industry. *Aquaculture, Fish and Fisheries* 2023:1-12.

influence site selection for such activities is salinity and the tolerance of the species to varying salinities. Although Echinodermata is a stenohaline phyla, several species show remarkable abilities to acclimate and survive in euryhaline habitats. *Tripneustes gratilla* is suggested to be sensitive to low salinities and freshwater inputs into the ocean are regarded as an important ocean barrier affecting the distribution and evolution of *Tripneustes*⁵³. Therefore, it has become important to understand how varying salinity affects the local species *Tripneustes gratilla*, as this may affect site selection for hatcheries and grow-out of the species — particularly along the warmer east coast of South Africa where there is an abundance of small rivers and estuaries along the coast. This trial therefore determined whether *T. gratilla* can tolerate and survive varying salinities (40-15‰) as well as how this exposure affects the immunity of the urchins subjected to these conditions.

Cultured sea urchins (30-80 mm test diameter) produced at the Marine Research Aquarium in Sea Point were used for the acute salinity trials. Sea urchins (10 replicates per treatment, n=60 urchins) for the acute exposure trials were exposed to four hypo-saline treatments (30, 25, 20 and 15 ppt salinity), one hyper-saline treatment (40 ppt) and a control treatment (35 ppt salinity). Six 11 litre glass aquarium tanks were used to conduct the trials and each tank was fitted with an aeration stone for oxygen and water movement. The salinity in each treatment was decreased or increased over a one-hour period by adding either fresh (non-chlorinated) water or hypersaline water. Flow rates were as follows: 40‰; 30‰ (2 L.hr⁻¹); 25‰ (4 L.hr⁻¹); 20‰ (6 L.hr⁻¹) and 15‰ (8 L.hr⁻¹). The 35‰ control was supplied with regular sea water (2 L.hr⁻¹). Behavioural responses of urchins were monitored throughout the 1-hour exposure trial in 10-minute increments. Urchin righting time was determined over a 30-minute period after the desired salinity had been achieved (after 1 hr) in each tank. A righting time response of 30-minutes was done in accordance with previous studies conducted on sea star and sea urchin^{54,55} to determine a response to salinity stress. Righting Activity Coefficients (AC = $1000 \times s^{-1}$) for 30-minutes will have a minimum righting time response 0.56 ($1000/1800$)⁵⁴. The higher righting time was assumed to indicate increased stress on the animal. Immediately following the righting response experiment, a coelomic fluid sample (~200 µL) was withdrawn to record total salinity and osmolality of the coelomic fluid samples. At the end of the acute (1.5 hrs) exposure trial, six sea urchins from each salinity treatment were injected with a sub-lethal dose of *Vibrio anguillarum* to

⁵³ Lessios H.A., Kane J., Robertson D.R., 2003. Phylogeography of the pantropical sea urchin *Tripneustes*: contrasting patterns of population structure between oceans. *Evolution* 57:2026-2036.

⁵⁴ Lawrence J.M., Cowell B.C., 1996. The righting response as an indication of stress in *Stichaster striatus* (Echinodermata, Asteroidea). *Marine and Freshwater Behaviour and Physiology* 27:239-248.

⁵⁵ Santos I.A., Castellano G.C., Freire C.A., 2013. Comparative Biochemistry and Physiology, Part A Direct relationship between osmotic and ionic conforming behaviour and tissue water regulatory capacity in echinoids. *Comparative Biochemistry and Physiology, Part A* 164:466-476.

determine the effect of varying salinity on the overall immune response of the urchins (i.e., the ability of the animal to render the injected dose of the bacterium non-culturable within a 30-minute period).

*Trial 4 – Develop and optimise culture technology to produce a new high value species, the tropical sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla*, in IMTA systems with *Ulva lacinulata**

Task 1 — Construct the first pilot-commercial scale sea urchin-*Ulva* IMTA production system in South Africa at Buffeljags Abalone farm. The design of this system was based on the existing abalone-*Ulva* IMTA systems that have operated successfully at Buffeljags Abalone for over a decade, but the system was scaled accordingly to fit within a tunnel system. The tunnel system was essential for the conservation of heat in order to cultivate the warm water sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla* in a temperate environment. The system was designed to be a recirculating aquaculture system integrated with an *Ulva* paddle-raceway, based on a similar design to the abalone-*Ulva* IMTA, and was equipped with a drum-filter, to remove large particulates prior to *Ulva* bioremediation, a heat-pump and a sump. The system allowed for the testing of a number of important functionality aspects to do with sea urchin-*Ulva* integration, including: 1) cycling of nutrients (N, P, ammonia, etc.) in both the sea urchin and *Ulva* tanks; 2) nutritional content and growth rate of *Ulva* under different conditions (recirculation rate, temperatures, nutrient loading, stocking density; and 3) optimal harvesting rates of *Ulva*. The system was designed in such a way that the volume of water moving between the urchin grow-out and *Ulva* raceways could be adjusted to determine the optimal circulation rate; without compromising growth or health of the system.

Task 2 — Optimise feeds, daily feeding rations and feeding frequency for full life-cycle grow-out of *Tripneustes gratilla* in the pilot commercial IMTA at Buffeljags Abalone farm. Juvenile sea urchins (ca. 2 mm test diameter, ± 450 urchins) were obtained from the Buffeljags Abalone hatchery and moved to Sea Point Marine Research Aquarium (MRA) for feeding trials in September 2022. Three different feeds, namely Kelp (*Ecklonia maxima*), IMTA grown *Ulva lacinulata*, and a formulated feed supplemented with 20% (w/w) dried *Ulva* were tested⁵⁶. *Ulva* was obtained from the IMTA systems at Buffeljags Abalone and kept in holding tanks at the MRA. Known quantities of feed were fed daily and all uneaten feed was removed 24 h after feeding, dried to a constant weight, and weighted to calculate consumption rates. Somatic growth was recorded weekly.

A separate trial was also conducted at the MRA to determine the effects of feeding frequency and feed volume offered to *T. gratilla* over a 2-month period. Urchins were initially stocked at 3.5 kg.m⁻². The treatments consisted of urchins fed frequently (daily) or infrequently (2 times a week) with a high,

⁵⁶ Cyrus M.D., Bolton J.J., Scholtz R., Macey B.M., 2015. The advantages of *Ulva* (Chlorophyta) as an additive in sea urchin formulated feeds: effects on palatability, consumption and digestibility. *Aquaculture Nutrition*. 21:578-591.

medium or low feed volume. *Ulva* was feed to urchins in the high-volume treatments at 7% of their body weight, while those in the medium- and low-volume treatments were fed at 5% and 2% of their body weight, respectively.

Task 3 — Optimize culture technology for the production of a new high value species, the sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla*, in the newly constructed pilot commercial IMTA systems at Buffeljags Abalone. Using all the information generated to date at a research scale (as well as data from the preliminary trials in the pilot commercial system), this trial aimed to assess the use of different feeds and feeding regimes on somatic growth (test diameter, and urchin weight) and gonad production (e.g., size, colour, texture, amino acid profile, taste) of *Tripneustes gratilla* under specific stocking densities and basket designs in a commercial setting. In order to stock the pilot IMTA commercial system at Buffeljags Abalone, large-scale production of *T. gratilla* juveniles was necessary — which allowed for further refinement of the hatchery technologies of this species for commercial scale production. Urchin broodstock were conditioned and spawned at the hatcheries in Sea Point as well as Buffeljags Abalone. Spawning was conducted in Jan/Feb 2023 and the spawning, larval rearing and settlement conducted were carried out as described in the ASTRAL deliverable D2.8.

This trial assessed the use of different feeds and feeding regimes on *T. gratilla* somatic growth (test diameter, and urchin weight) and gonad production (e.g., size, colour, texture, amino acid profile, taste) under specific stocking densities (8 kg.m²) and basket designs (Internal service area (ISA) = 1.69m²) in a commercial system. The latter parameters were selected based on preliminary trials conducted in 2021/2022 (see trial 1 in this report). This trial was divided into two phases, a somatic growth phase (ca. 6-months; commenced on the 14th August 2023) and a gonad enhancement phase (ca. 3-months; commenced on the 22nd February 2024), with different combinations of feeds tested during each phase, including: 1) Fresh *Ulva* (FU) from zero to five months (Somatic growth phase), then finished off with pellets (20% dried *Ulva* inclusion diet formulated by Cyrus et al.⁵⁷, made by feed producer 1) for four months (Gonad enhancement phase) [FU-20UF1]; 2) Fresh *Ulva* (FU) from zero to five months, then finished off with pellets (20% dried *Ulva* inclusion diet formulated by Cyrus et al.⁵², made by feed producer 2) for four months [FU-20UF2]; 3) Mixed feeding regime of FU and 20UF1 over the entire 9-month production cycle; 4) Mixed feeding regime of FU and 20UF2 over the entire 9-month production cycle; and 5) Mixed feeding regime of FU and AquaVitae formulated feed over the entire 9-month production cycle made by feed producer 2 [M-AVF3]. Urchins were stocked in four raceways (6×1.8×0.8 m, 8.5 m³; L×W×D), each containing 20 baskets (0.8×0.5×0.5 m, L×W×D) so that

⁵⁷ Cyrus M.D., Bolton J.J., Macey B.M., De Wet L., 2014. The development of a formulated feed containing *Ulva* (Chlorophyta) to promote rapid growth and enhanced production of high quality roe in the sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla* (Linnaeus). *Aquaculture Research* 45:159-176.

each feeding regime was replicated four times in each raceway. All urchins were weaned on a diet of fresh IMTA *Ulva* prior to the start of the feeding trial, which commenced on 14th August 2023. Baskets were weighed weekly to adjust feeding rates (ca. 1% BW.day⁻¹ for formulated feeds and 6% BW.day⁻¹ for *Ulva*). Somatic growth was recorded monthly from zero to five months, whereas both somatic and gonad growth/development were recorded monthly thereafter. Somatic growth was recorded using the computer vision programme described in Trial 2 above. Briefly, between 12 and 30 urchins were placed in a pre-weighted Styrofoam box and the total weight of all animals recorded before photographing the animals. A reference disc (of known diameter) was placed in the top right-hand corner of the box prior to photographing. Average weight (in g) and test diameter (in mm) was determined as described by de Vos et al.⁵⁸. To determine gonad somatic index (GSI), immediately prior to and during the gonad enhancement phase of the study, a single urchin was randomly removed from each treatment in each raceway tank (n=4 per treatment). After recording the total wet weight of each urchin, a single gonad from each urchin was randomly selected and transferred into Davidson's Fixative (per litre: 300 mL 95% ethyl alcohol, 200 mL 100% formalin, 100 mL glycerol, 100 mL glacial acetic acid and 300 mL distilled water) immediately following dissection and fixed for 48 h, before being transferred into 70% ethanol and processed for routine paraffin histology⁵⁹. Histological analysis was conducted according to Cyrus et al.⁶⁰ to determine the amount of gametogenic activity in the gonads of urchins fed the various diets, with high quality sea urchin gonads considered to be those which contain little to no gametogenic activity. The density of nutritive phagocytes (NP) within each gonad was calculated to determine whether the density of NP within each gonad differs between the feeding regimes or stages of gonad maturity (as described in Cyrus et al.⁶⁰).

4.2.3 Results

Trial 1 – Optimising basket depth and stocking density for the production of Tripneustes gratilla

Basket depth had no significant effect on spine loss ($P=0.842$), whereas feed type did ($P<0.001$) — with the kelp fed animals displaying significantly higher spine loss than urchins fed the pelleted formulated feed (Figure 21A). Furthermore, when looking at the impact of basket removal time on urchin spine loss (urchins were not fed throughout these experiments), we found no significant difference in spine

⁵⁸ De Vos B., Cyrus M.D., Macey B.M., Batik T., Bolton J.J., 2023. Combining computer vision and standardised protocols for improved measurement of live sea urchins for research and industry. *Aquaculture, Fish and Fisheries* 2023:1-12.

⁵⁹ Bucke D., 1989. Histology. In: Austin, B., Austin, D.A. (Eds.), *Methods for the Microbiological Examination of Fish and Shellfish*. Ellis Horwood, Chichester, pp. 69-97.

⁶⁰ Cyrus M.D., Bolton J.J., Macey B.M., De Wet L., 2014. The development of a formulated feed containing *Ulva* (Chlorophyta) to promote rapid growth and enhanced production of high quality roe in the sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla* (Linnaeus). *Aquaculture Research* 45:159-176.

loss between the control (not removed from the water at all) and the short (five second) basket removal treatment (Figure 21B). Conversely, animals removed for longer periods of time (five-minute removal daily) had significantly higher spine loss ($P < 0.001$).

Figure 21. Average daily spine loss of *Tripnesutes gratilla* maintained in either shallow (15cm) or deep (30cm) baskets (A) when fed three different feed types, namely kelp (*Ecklonia maxima*), a pelleted formulated feed, or fresh *Ulva lacunculata* and (B) in response to three different basket removal treatments, including none (not removed from the water), short (five-second removal daily) and long (five-minute removal daily). The different subscripts above each box plot represent significant differences between the mean spine loss of urchins within each treatment group.

Literature suggests biomass production of various urchin species is reduced when cultivated in deeper baskets. The present study confirmed these findings, with deeper baskets resulting in significantly lower consumption of various feed types ($P < 0.026$) (Figure 22A & B). Collectively, these data suggest consumption and removal of baskets for extended periods are the primary cause of decreased production in deeper baskets.

Figure 22. The average daily consumption of the pelleted formulated feed (A) and fresh *Ulva lacinulata* (B) by *Tripneustes gratilla* housed in deep (30cm) and shallow (15cm) baskets (C). Different subscripts above the box plots represent significant differences in consumption between treatments.

After determining the optimal basket depth for biomass production, the next step was to determine optimal stocking density. Separate trials were conducted to assess impacts of different feed types (*Ulva* vs. pellets) at varying stocking density (13, 19 and 24% coverage of the internal surface area (ISA) of the basket) on production over a 3-month period. Urchins fed *Ulva* and maintained at a low stocking density had an average mass specific growth rate (SGR) of ca. 0.2 g.d⁻¹, which was significantly higher (P=0.031) than the medium and high stocking density treatments (Figure 23A). At the end of the 3-month trial, urchins in the low density occupied ca. 22% of the ISA of the baskets. However, when one looks at the total basket mass, it is evident that the greater the initial stocking density the greater the total urchin yield at the end of the trials/ production period (Figure 23B). Moreover, if one looks at the net predicted gonad yield at end of the trail, almost double the amount of gonad was produced in the high stocking density treatment when compared to the low stocking density treatment (Figure 23C). While higher stocking densities did significantly reduce mass SGR, mortality, cannibalism, and gonad size/quality were not influenced by stocking density (see de Vos et al.⁶¹ for detailed results).

⁶¹ De Vos, B., Cyrus, M.D., Bolton, J.J., Macey, B.M. (2023) Effect of basket height and stocking density on production of the sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla*: insights and recommendations. *Aquaculture International*. Published Online: <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10499-024-01412-8>.

Figure 23. The effect of low (4 kgs.m⁻²), medium (6 kgs.m⁻²) and high (8 kgs.m⁻²) stocking densities on (A) the mass specific growth rate (SGR) of *Tripneustes gratilla*, (B) the total mass of all urchins in a basket (B), and the net predicted gonad yield (g.m⁻² basket ISA) over a period of three months. Different subscripts above box plots represent significant differences between the means of treatment groups.

Trial 2 – Development of a computer vision programme for improved measurement of live sea urchins

Data from these trials revealed that urchin wet mass can vary up to 8.73% depending on time out of water. The greatest differences observed were between the five second and the 10-minute weighing ($P < 0.001$), while no significant differences were observed between the latter time intervals (Figure 24; $P < 0.05$). Drip loss is significantly reduced to an average of 0.1% change by allowing urchins to drip-dry for at least 90 s prior to weighing.

Figure 24. Logarithmic function representing the percentage reduction in mass averaged between nine urchins weighed at various times following removal from a body of water ($y = -0.013\ln(x) + 1.0153$, $R^2 = 0.97$). The percentage value was determined by dividing the mass of each urchin at individual time points by its initial mass at five seconds.

When comparing the various traditional methods for measuring urchins with the computer vision programme, we found the conventional vernier calliper method for measuring urchin dimensions both time-consuming and imprecise (mean coefficient of variation (CV) of 2.41% for *Tripneustes gratilla*). Conversely, the computer vision programme developed in this trial measured with higher precision (mean CV of 1.55% for *T. gratilla*) and was shown to be considerably faster (Figure 25).

Figure 25. Box plots comparing the distribution of coefficient of variation between various measurement methods for *Tripneustes gratilla*. M.O. = multiple operators, S.O. = single operator, and T.B. = total basket mass. Different subscripts denote a significant difference in the coefficients of variation between methods (Height measurements were not included in the statistical analysis, hence there are no subscripts above the box plots).

Trial 3 – The effects of acute and chronic exposure to varying salinities (15-40‰) on behaviour, physiology, health (immunity) and growth of Tripneustes gratilla

Sea urchins are known as stenohaline and osmo-conforming organisms and are rare habitants of estuarine or lower salinity environments^{62,63,64,65}. *Tripneustes gratilla* in the current study were acutely exposed (over a period of 1-hour) to four hypo-saline treatments (30, 25, 20 and 15 ppt salinity), a hyper-saline treatment (40 ppt) and a control treatment (35 ppt salinity). The salinity of the coelomic fluid decreased significantly over this time-period with the decrease in salinity of the surrounding seawater (Figure 26A). Salinity had a significant impact on the behaviour of *Tripneustes*, as shown by

⁶² Stickle W.B., Ahokas R., 1974. The effects of tidal fluctuation of salinity on the perivisceral fluid composition of several echinoderms. *Comparative Biochemistry and Physiology Part Physiology* 47:469-476.

⁶³ Himmelman J.H., Lavergne Y., Axelsen F., Cardinal A., Bourget E., 1983. Sea urchins in the saint lawrence estuary: their abundance, size-structure, and suitability for commercial exploitation. *Canadian Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Sciences* 40: 474-486.

⁶⁴ Roller R.A., Stickle W.B., 1994. Effects of adult salinity acclimation on larval survival and early development of *Strongylocentrotus droebachiensis* and *Strongylocentrotus pallidus* (Echinodermata, Echinoidea). *Canadian Journal of Zoology-Revue Canadienne De Zoologie* 72:1931-1939.

⁶⁵ Russell M.P., 2013. Echinoderm responses to variation in salinity. *Advances in Marine Biology* 66:171-212.

the change in righting behaviour — with righting response (activity coefficient) declining at salinities above and below the 35 ppt control (Figure 26B). Urchins exposed to salinities below 20 ppt were not able to right themselves (ability of an urchin to rights itself from its aboral surface onto its oral surface using its tube feet) within the 30-minute assessment period.

Figure 26. Coelomic fluid salinity (ppt) (A) and the righting activity coefficient ($AC = 1000 \times s^{-1}$) (B) of *Tripneustes gratilla* acutely exposed (over a period of 1-hour) to four hypo-saline treatments (30, 25, 20 and 15ppt salinity), hypersaline treatment (40ppt), and a control treatment (35ppt salinity).

When assessing the impacts of salinity on the immune response of urchins, which was assessed as the ability of an urchin to render a known concentration of the injected bacterium *Vibrio anguillarum* non-culturable with a 30-minute period, it was shown that immunity was compromised at reduced salinities — i.e., urchins were less capable of rendering the injected dose of *Vibrio* non-culturable (Figure 27). This reduction in the clearance of *V. anguillarum* is indicative of stress and a compromised immune system.

Figure 27. Mean number of culturable bacteria remaining in haemolymph circulation of *Tripneustes gratilla* in each treatment at 30-minutes post-challenge with *Vibrio anguillarum*. Values are mean \pm S.E. (n=6-18 samples). Different letters indicate a significant difference ($P < 0.05$) between treatments (Holm-Sidak multiple comparison).

*Trial 4 – Develop and optimize culture technology to produce a new high value species, the tropical sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla*, in IMTA systems with *Ulva lacinulata**

*Task 1 – Construct a pilot-commercial scale sea urchin-*Ulva* IMTA production system at Buffeljags Abalone farm*

The pilot commercial scale sea urchin-*Ulva* IMTA was designed and successfully constructed at Buffeljags Abalone farm. The system was constructed to include 5×8000 L glass fibre tanks (Figure 28A & B) that are interconnected with a 14000 L *Ulva* paddle-raceway (Figure 28C) and a 14000 L sump (Figure 28B). The system is fitted with a drum-filter, protein skimmers and a heat-pump to maintain a constant temperature of ca. 24°C (Figure 28B). The entire system is housed within a tunnel to conserve heat (Figure 28D). Effluent water exiting each of the urchin tanks flows into the *Ulva* paddle-raceway, after passing through the drum-filter to remove larger particulates. The bio-remediated seawater exiting the *Ulva* paddle-raceway enters the sump before being recirculated back to the sea urchin tanks. Each of the glass fibre tanks is fitted with 20 baskets, which are suspended in the tanks.

Figure 28. Land-based pump-ashore IMTA system for the production of sea urchin (*Tripneustes gratilla*) and seaweed (*Ulva lacinulata*) at Buffeljags abalone. The photograph shows (A) the 8000 L glass fibre raceway tanks housing sea urchins; (B) the drum filter, protein skimmers, and sump; (C) *Ulva* paddle raceway; and (D) tunnel system housing all the aforementioned system components.

Task 2 – Optimise feeds and daily feeding rations for full life-cycle grow-out of Tripneustes gratilla in the pilot commercial IMTA at Buffeljags Abalone farm.

Trials assessing the effects of kelp (*Ecklonia maxima*), *Ulva lacinulata*, and the formulated feed supplemented with 20% (w/w) dried *Ulva*⁶⁶, revealed that there was a significant impact of feed on test diameter, with juveniles (initial TD ca. 2 cm) fed fresh IMTA *Ulva* and the formulated feed supplemented with 20% dried *Ulva* growing significantly faster than urchins fed kelp (Figure 29). Conversely, the highest feed consumption was recorded for urchins fed kelp ($10.58 \pm 2.01\% \text{ BW} \cdot \text{day}^{-1}$), followed by *Ulva* ($8.50 \pm 0.78\% \text{ BW} \cdot \text{day}^{-1}$) and formulated feed ($1.82 \pm 0.37\% \text{ BW} \cdot \text{day}^{-1}$).

Figure 29. Mean±SEM diameter (A) and feed consumption (%BW.day⁻¹) of *Tripneustes gratilla* fed with three experimental diets: FF= Formulated feed, KELP=fresh *Ecklonia maxima*, ULVA: fresh *Ulva lacinulata*. The shaded part of the graph represents the acclimation period before the administration of the experimental feeds.

⁶⁶ Cyrus M.D., Bolton J.J., Macey B.M., De Wet L., 2014. The development of a formulated feed containing *Ulva* (Chlorophyta) to promote rapid growth and enhanced production of high quality roe in the sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla* (Linnaeus). *Aquaculture Research* 45:159-176.

There was a significant impact of the feed on the gonad weight (Kruskal-Wallis, $P < 0.001$; $F = 16.722$) and the GSI (Kruskal-Wallis, $P < 0.001$; $F = 14.750$) at the end of the experimental period. The post-hoc multiple comparison analysis showed that urchins fed with formulated feed have significantly heavier gonads and a higher GSI than urchins in the other treatment groups. No significant differences in gonad weight and GSI were however observed between the *Ulva* and kelp treatments at the end of the trial. The average gonad weight and GSI was 1.6 ± 0.64 g and $4.69 \pm 1.88\%$ with formulated feed, respectively, 0.31 ± 0.08 g and $0.99 \pm 0.26\%$ with kelp, and 0.25 ± 0.19 g and $0.92 \pm 0.88\%$ with *Ulva* (Figure 30).

Figure 30. Box plots comparing the gonad weight (A) and gonad somatic index (GSI) (B) of *Tripneustes gratilla* fed three experimental diets: FF= Formulated feed, KELP=fresh *Ecklonia maxima*, ULVA: fresh *Ulva lacinulata*.

Trials to assess the effects of varying feeding frequency and feeding volume on *T. gratilla* growth and gonad weight revealed that feeding urchins a diet of *Ulva* at 7% of their body weight daily produced the highest specific growth rate (Figure 31). Gonad somatic indices (GSI) and gonad mass was also highest for urchins fed larger volumes of feed at higher frequencies (Figure 32).

Figure 31. Specific growth rates for test diameter, test height and total wet-weight (mean±SE) for the sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla* within the varying feeding frequency and feed volume treatments.

Figure 32. The gonad somatic index (GSI) and gonad wet weight (mean±SE) of *Tripneustes gratilla* within the varying feeding frequency and feed volume treatments.

Task 3 – Tripneustes gratilla grow-out studies in the pilot commercial IMTA at Buffeljags Abalone.

In order to produce sufficient numbers of *T. gratilla* juveniles to stock the pilot-commercial scale IMTA at Buffeljags Abalone (Figure 33), urchin broodstock were conditioned and spawned at the hatcheries in both Sea Point as well as Buffeljags Abalone. Spawning was conducted on four separate occasions — May, June, and September 2022 and finally in Jan/Feb 2023. Different rearing methods (static vs. flow-through systems), tanks designs (conical, flat-bottomed, & semi-spherical tanks), stocking densities, and aeration strategies (air-stones vs. bubbling through glass rods) were tested, as well as pelagic and benthic microalgae species for larval rearing and settlement, respectively. It was found that flow-through systems using conical and semi-spherical tanks promoted high larval survival when high quality seawater is available — reducing larval handling and providing more stable water quality through constant water exchange. Conversely, when access to high quality seawater is not available, static systems provide better control of water quality, but is more labour intensive. Approximately 25000-30000 juvenile sea urchins were successfully produced from the Jan/Feb spawning event to stock the IMTA at Buffeljags Abalone (see details below). A detailed production manual for the cultivation of the tropical and temperate sea urchin, which includes the hatchery and nursery stages, can be found in the ASTRAL deliverable D2.8.

Figure 33. (A) Sea urchin tunnel at the South African IMTA Lab; (B, C) juvenile sea urchins stocked into the system; (D,E) baskets holding sea urchins that are measured on a weekly basis; (F) sea urchin gonads/product. ©UCT/DFFE

The average diameter of an individual urchin at the start of the full life-cycle grow-out trial in the pilot commercial IMTA at Buffeljags Abalone was 34.90 mm. After 8-months of being fed the various experimental feeds, the mean diameter of the urchins increased to 59.79, 58.47, 59.21, 57.38 and 55.73 mm for the FU-20UF1, FU-20UF2, 20UF1, 20UF2, and M-AVF3 treatments, respectively (Figure 34A). Urchins fed the FU-20UF1 ($P=0.021$) and the 20UF1 ($P=0.048$) diets had test diameters that were significantly greater than urchins fed the M-AVF3 by month eight of the trial. No significant differences were however recorded between any of the other treatment groups. The average diameter SGR across all treatments was $0.287 \text{ mm} \cdot \text{d}^{-1}$ (Figure 35A) and no significant difference ($P=0.462$) in diameter SGR were recorded between any of the treatment groups. Similar trends were recorded for urchin mass. At the start of the trial, the mean mass of the urchins was 20.00 g, and by 8-months the mean mass had increased to 88.28, 87.92, 90.63, 84.62 and 78.52 g for the FU-20UF1, FU-20UF2, 20UF1, 20UF2, and M-AVF3 treatments, respectively (Figure 34B). No significant differences were however recorded between the mean mass of urchins in the various treatments at any of the sampling times. The average mass SGR of urchins across all treatments was $0.78 \text{ g} \cdot \text{d}^{-1}$ (Figure 35B), with no significant difference in

mass SGR recorded between any of the treatment groups. These trials provided no indication that the tested feeds and feeding regimes had any effect on the mass and diameter SGR of *T. gratilla*.

Figure 34. *Tripneustes gratilla* (A) mean±SEM diameter in mm and (B) mean±SEM individual weights in g over the 8-month experimental period, as well as the (C) mean±SEM gonad somatic index (GS) of urchins during the gonad enhancement phase (month 6, 7 and 8) of the trial. Dietary treatments included: 1) Fresh *Ulva* (FU) from zero to six months (Somatic growth phase), then finished off with pellets from feed manufacturer 1 from month 6 onwards [FU-20UF1]; 2) Fresh *Ulva* (FU) from zero to six months, then finished off with pellets (20U feed from feed manufacturer 2) from month six onwards [FU-20UF2]; 3) Mixed feeding regime of FU and 20UF1 over the entire production cycle [20UF1]; 4) Mixed feeding regime of FU and 20UM over the entire production cycle [20UF2]; and 5) Mixed feeding regime of FU and AquaVitae formulated feed over the entire production cycle [M-AVF3]. The shaded portion of the graph represents the change in diet within the feeding regimes.

Figure 35. The effect of various feeds and feeding regimes on the diameter (A) and mass (B) specific growth rate of *Tripneustes gratilla* over the 8-month experimental period. Dietary treatments included: 1) Fresh *Ulva* (FU) from zero to six months (Somatic growth phase), then finished off with pellets from feed manufacturer 1 from month 6 onwards [FU-20UF1]; 2) Fresh *Ulva* (FU) from zero to six months, then finished off with pellets (20U feed from feed manufacturer 2) from month six onwards [FU-20UF2]; 3) Mixed feeding regime of FU and 20UF1 over the entire production cycle [20UF1]; 4) Mixed feeding regime of FU and 20UM over the entire production cycle [20UF2]; and 5) Mixed feeding regime of FU and AquaVitae formulated feed over the entire production cycle [M-AVF3].

After approximately 6-month of feeding the various experimental feeds (somatic growth phase of the trial), urchins in the treatments fed solely on fresh IMTA grown *Ulva lacunculata*, the FU-20UF1 and FU-20UF2 treatments, were switched over to pellets (20UF1 and 20UF2 pelleted diets, respectively). This coincided with the start of the gonad enhancement phase, where gonad mass is increased prior to market. Immediately prior to the start of the gonad enhancement (at 6-months) and every month thereafter, an urchin from each treatment within each raceway (n=4 per treatment) was sacrificed to determine the change in gonad somatic index (GSI). The GSI of urchins fed the mixed diet of FU and 20UF1 had a significantly higher GSI compared with the FU-20UF2 (P=0.024) and M-AVF3 (P=0.006) treatments immediately prior to the gonad enhancement, however by month eight of the trial the GSI of urchins in all treatments was similar and no significant difference between treatments were recorded (Figure 34C).

4.2.4 Discussion and Conclusion

Optimising stocking density is crucial for maximising yield, consistency, and quality of sea urchin gonads as well as the welfare of urchins in a commercial production system. A crucial and related factor for successful echinoculture is basket height. *Tripneustes gratilla*, as with other urchin species, tend to congregate on the side walls of baskets, and previous studies have suggested that deep baskets cause more collisions between urchins, resulting in increased spine loss which reduces urchin production. Other studies suggest adverse impacts of deep baskets on consumption, as urchins must travel further to feed, and finally it has been suggested that when you have deep baskets there is higher damage during basket removal and routine cleaning^{67, 68, 69, 70, 71, 72}. However, none of these theories have been investigated empirically for *T. gratilla* prior to this study.

Contrary to Siikavuopio's⁷¹ theory, these trials revealed that basket depth did not result in significantly higher spine loss in *T. gratilla*, but feed type did. Urchins fed kelp (*Ecklonia maxima*) in our trials had significantly higher spine loss compared with urchins fed the pelleted diet or fresh IMTA grown *Ulva lacunculata* — regardless of the basket depths tested in this trial. We hypothesise that this is attributed to increased spine damage and loss when uneaten kelp is removed from baskets during routine cleaning as well as competition between urchins when feeding on the ridged, larger pieces of kelp. The increased spine loss resulting from this feed type could negatively impact somatic growth and reproduction, as has been suggested by others^{73, 74, 75, 76}. When looking at impact of basket removal, we found no significant difference between the five second (short) basket removal time versus the control treatment, where baskets containing urchins were not removed from water at all. Conversely,

⁶⁷ Devin M.G., 2002. Land-based echinoculture: A novel system to culture adult sea urchins. In: Yokota Y., Matranga V., Smolenicka Z. (Eds) The sea urchin: From basic biology to aquaculture, pp 145-159.

⁶⁸ Pearce C.M., Daggett T.L., Robinson S.M.C., 2002. Optimizing prepared feed ration for gonad production of the green sea urchin *Strongylocentrotus droebachiensis*. Journal of the World Aquaculture Society 33:268-277.

⁶⁹ Daggett T.L., Pearce C.M., Robinson S.M.C., 2006. A comparison of three land-based containment systems for use in culturing green sea urchins, *Strongylocentrotus droebachiensis* (Muller) (Echinodermata: Echinoidea). Aquaculture Research 37:339-350.

⁷⁰ Christiansen J.S., Siikavuopio S.I., 2007. The relationship between feed intake and gonad growth of single and stocked green sea urchin (*Strongylocentrotus droebachiensis*) in a raceway culture. Aquaculture 262:163-167.

⁷¹ Siikavuopio S., Dale T., Mortensen A., 2007. The effects of stocking density on gonad growth, survival and feed intake of adult green sea urchin (*Strongylocentrotus droebachiensis*). Aquaculture 262:78-85.

⁷² Siikavuopio S., 2009. Green sea urchin (*Strongylocentrotus droebachiensis*, Müller) in aquaculture: the effects of environmental factors on gonad growth. PhD thesis, University of Tromsø, Tromsø.

⁷³ Ebert T.A., 1967. Negative growth and longevity in the purple sea urchin *Strongylocentrotus purpuratus* (Stimpson). Science 157:557-558.

⁷⁴ Ebert T.A., 1968. Growth rates of the sea urchin *Strongylocentrotus purpuratus* related to food availability and spine abrasion. Ecology 49:1075-1091.

⁷⁵ Edwards P.B., Ebert T.A., 1991. Plastic responses to limited food availability and spine damage in the sea urchin *Strongylocentrotus purpuratus* (Stimpson). Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology 145:205-220.

⁷⁶ Haag N., Russell M.P., Hernandez J.C., 2016. Effects of spine damage and microhabitat on resource allocation of the purple sea urchin *Strongylocentrotus purpuratus* (Stimpson 1857). Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology 482:106-117.

baskets containing animals that were removed from the water for longer periods of time (five-minute removal daily) had significantly higher spine loss. The increased spine loss is mostly attributed to the damage caused to urchins falling to the bottom of the baskets when they are removed from the tanks, suggesting that shallower baskets (<20 cm) should be used for commercial production of *Tripneustes*, as well as other sea urchin species. This recommendation is further supported by the observation of decreased consumption of both *Ulva* and a pelleted feed in deeper baskets. Collectively, these data suggest consumption and removal of baskets for extended periods are the primary cause of decreased production in deeper baskets.

After determining the effects of basket depth on production, the next step was to determine optimal stocking density. We tested three different stocking densities, guided by available information in the literature and preliminary experiments we had conducted. The stocking densities included a low, medium and high density of 4, 6 and 8 kg.m⁻², which equates too roughly 13, 19 and 24% coverage of available internal surface area (ISA) of a basket. While higher stocking densities (6 and 8 kg.m⁻²) did significantly reduce mass SGR ($P < 0.044$), mortality, cannibalism and gonad size as well as quality were not influenced by the stocking densities tested in this trial. Difference in SGR are attributed to spine loss from negative behavioural interactions. Contrary to the adverse impact of higher stocking densities on SGR, the total mass of urchins and gonad yield by the end of the 3-month trial was significantly larger in the greater stocking densities. Based on these findings we suggest that the optimal stocking density will differ depending on the primary objective of the farmer. If the objective is to have each individual urchin gain as much mass as possible, then a low density of approximately 15% cover is ideal. Conversely, if the objective is to gain as much total urchin mass and gonad material as possible, then a higher stocking density of approximately 20% coverage of the ISA of baskets should be used during the grow-out phase of a *T. gratilla* production cycle.

The computer vision protocol developed in this study was shown to significantly increase the precision and decrease the time required for estimating average urchin diameter and mass in a commercial setting. The software uses a series of hue saturation value filters, edge detection algorithms and distortions to measure the diameter of the test (excluding spines) of multiple urchins at once⁷⁷. The software is open-source, and the protocol does not require specialised equipment — can be performed with a mobile phone camera. The computer vision programme was shown to be at least three times faster than the manual calliper method for measuring urchin diameter and is more precise and efficient. To achieve maximum precision of wet mass measurements, we suggest weighing urchins

⁷⁷ De Vos B., Cyrus M.D., Macey B.M., Batik T., Bolton J.J., 2023. Combining computer vision and standardised protocols for improved measurement of live sea urchins for research and industry. *Aquaculture, Fish and Fisheries* 2023:1-12.

anytime between 90 s and 120 s after removal from the water to allow them sufficient time to drip-dry before weighing. The trials also found no significant difference between mass before and after feeding, suggesting it is not necessary to purge animals (via starvation) prior to weighing. However, to improve efficiency of measurement (as all feed should be removed from urchins prior to photographing), it is recommended that urchins are not fed the day before measurements. Use of the computer vision protocol over traditional methods of measurement will result in reduced handling stress and spine loss of urchins (which could decrease urchin growth when done routinely on a farm), and ultimately improve efficiency of measuring and grading animals on a farm. There is also significant potential for adapting this technology to automated grading systems on commercial farms and for measuring and grading other farmed aquatic organisms, such as abalone.

Environmental factors such as salinity and temperature play a major role in the distribution of natural sea urchin stocks and for the pantropical shallow water echinoid *Tripneustes*, freshwater inputs (rivers) along the coastline are regarded as a major barrier for the distribution of species within the genus⁷⁸. Within a culture environment, sub-optimal conditions such as acute changes in salinity, temperature and oxygen can also negatively influence the welfare and productivity of sea urchins, having major effects on immunity, behaviour and ultimately the survival of sea urchins^{79, 80, 81}. It has long been assumed that echinoderms are exclusively stenohaline, meaning that they do not have a wide tolerance of changes in salinity. Echinoderms do not have the structural capability to regulate or maintain the salinity (concentration of salts) of their internal coelomic fluids when exposed to varied salinity concentrations and thus are considered to be typically isosmotic and osmo-conformer organisms^{82, 83, 84, 85}. This is primarily due to sea urchins having a permeable body wall, and lacking a differentiated osmoregulatory and excretory organ^{86, 84}. The findings from this trial support these notions, as we demonstrate a significant reduction in the salinity of the coelomic fluid of *T. gratilla*

⁷⁸ Lessios H.A., Kane J., Robertson D.R., 2003. Phylogeography of the pantropical sea urchin *Tripneustes*: Contrasting patterns of population structure between oceans. *Evolution* 57: 2026-2036.

⁷⁹ McBride S.C. 2005. Sea Urchin Aquaculture. *American Fisheries Society Symposium*. 46:179-208

⁸⁰ Rahman S., Tsuchiya M. and Uehara T., 2009. Effects of temperature on hatching rate, embryonic development and early larval survival of the edible sea urchin, *Tripneustes gratilla*. *Biologia*, 64:768-775.

⁸¹ Shannon R., Mustafa A. 2015. A comparison of stress susceptibility of sea urchins and sea cucumbers in aquaculture conditions. *Bioengineering and Bioscience*, 3:100-107.

⁸² Roller R.A., Stickle W.B., 1994. Effects of adult salinity acclimation on larval survival and early development of *Strongylocentrotus droebachiensis* and *Strongylocentrotus pallidus* (Echinodermata: Echinoidea). *Canadian Journal of Zoology* 72:1931-1939.

⁸³ Diehl W.J., 1986. Osmoregulation in echinoderms. *Comparative Biochemistry and Physiology -- Part A: Physiology*, 84:199-205.

⁸⁴ Roller R.A., Stickle W.B., 1993. Effects of salinity on larval survival, physiology, and early development. *Marine Biology*, 116:583-591.

⁸⁵ Vidolin D., Santos-gouveia I.A., Freire C.A., 2007. Differences in ion regulation in the sea urchins *Lytechinus variegatus* and *Arbacia lixula* (Echinodermata: Echinoidea). *Journal of the Marine Biological Association of the United Kingdom* 87:769-775.

⁸⁶ Stickle W.B., Ahokas R., 1974. The effects of tidal fluctuation of salinity on the perivisceral fluid composition of several echinoderms. *Comparative Biochemistry and Physiology -- Part A: Physiology*, 47:469-476.

following acute (1-hour) exposure to decreasing external salinities that were accompanied by significant changes in urchin behaviour — i.e., a significant reduction in righting response with decreasing salinities. Righting times have been used in previous studies to assess the health status of sea urchins^{87, 88}, using a protocol initially developed for sea stars^{89, 90}. A healthy urchin will use its podia and spines, when inverted, to right itself onto its oral surface. This process requires a high degree of neuromuscular coordination and when hindered, are much slower, in unhealthy or diseased urchins or urchins subjected to stress^{91, 92, 93}, including salinity stress. The reduction in righting response observed in our trials is an indication of potential adverse impacts on the water vascular system of urchins⁹⁴ and increased stress following acute exposure to reduced salinity. Indeed, it has been shown that osmotic pressure and ionic imbalances are regulated by the intracellular uptake of ions⁹⁵. We further demonstrated that acute exposure to hypo-saline conditions (30, 25, 20 and 15ppt salinity) compromises the immune response of *T. gratilla*, reducing its ability to render an injected dose of bacteria non-culturable. The bacterial challenge assay utilised in this study has previously been used to successfully assess the effects of a variety of environmental stressors on the immune response of several invertebrates, including blue crabs⁹⁶, oysters⁹⁷ and more recently crayfish⁹⁸. The results from these trials suggest that careful consideration must be made with regards to site selection when farming this species, avoiding sites located close to estuaries where salinities are either periodically or frequently impacted by rainfall events.

⁸⁷ Himmelman J.H., Lavergne Y., Axelsen, F., Cardinal A., Bourget E., 1983. Sea urchins in the saint lawrence estuary: their abundance, size-structure, and suitability for commercial exploitation. Canadian Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Sciences, 40:474-486.

⁸⁸ Santos I.A., Castellano G.C., Freire C.A., 2013. Comparative Biochemistry and Physiology, Part A Direct relationship between osmotic and ionic conforming behaviour and tissue water regulatory capacity in echinoids. Comparative Biochemistry and Physiology, Part A, 164:466-476.

⁸⁹ Lawrence J.M., Cowell B.C., 1996. The righting response as an indication of stress in *Stichaster striatus* (Echinodermata, Asteroidea). Marine and Freshwater Behaviour and Physiology, 27:239-248.

⁹⁰ Barker, M.F., Russell, M.P., 2008. The distribution and behaviour of *Patiriella mortenseni* and *P. regularis* in the extreme hyposaline conditions of the Southern New Zealand Fiords. Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology 355:76-84.

⁹¹ Himmelman J.H., Lavergne Y., Axelsen, F., Cardinal A. and Bourget E. 1983. Sea urchins in the saint lawrence estuary: their abundance, size-structure, and suitability for commercial exploitation. Canadian Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Sciences 40:474-486.

⁹² Himmelman J.H., Guderley H., Vignault G., Drouin G., Wells P.G. 1984. Importance of size, acclimation, and interpopulation differences. Canadian Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Sciences, 62:1015-1921.

⁹³ Stickle W.B., Diehl W.J., 1987. Effects of salinity on echinoderms. Echinoderm Studies 2:235-285.

⁹⁴ Pawson, D.L., Améziane, N., Vance, D.J., Baker, A.N., Clark, H.E.S., Davey, N., 2007. Phylum Echinodermata: Sea-stars, Brittelstars, Sea Urchins, Sea Cucumbers, Sea Lilies, and Kin, January.

⁹⁵ Vidolin D., Santos-gouvea I.A., Freire C.A., 2007. Differences in ion regulation in the sea urchins *Lytechinus variegatus* and *Arbacia lixula* (Echinodermata: Echinoidea). Journal of the Marine Biological Association of the United Kingdom 87:769-775.

⁹⁶ Macey B.M., Rathburn C.K., Thibodeaux L.K., Burnett L.E., Burnett K.G., 2008b. Clearance of *Vibrio campbellii* injected into the hemolymph of *Callinectes sapidus*, the Atlantic blue crab: The effects of prior exposure to bacteria and environmental hypoxia. Fish and Shellfish Immunology 25:718-730.

⁹⁷ Macey B.M., Achilihu I.O., Burnett K.G., Burnett, L.E., 2008a. Effects of hypercapnic hypoxia on inactivation and elimination of *Vibrio campbellii* in the Eastern oyster, *Crassostrea virginica*. Applied and Environmental Microbiology 74:6077-6084.

⁹⁸ Knapp, J.L., Auerswald, L., Hoffman, L.C., Macey, B.M., 2019. Effects of chronic hypercapnia and elevated temperature on the immune response of the spiny lobster, *Jasus lalandii*. Fish and Shellfish Immunology 93:752-762.

Trials assessing the effects of kelp (*Ecklonia maxima*), *Ulva lacinulata*, and the formulated feed supplemented with 20% (w/w) dried *Ulva*⁹⁹ revealed that there was a significant impact of feed on test diameter, with urchins fed fresh *Ulva* and the pelleted feed growing equally well but significantly better than animal fed with kelp. This is the first study to assess the effects of kelp on the somatic growth of *T. gratilla*. Previous studies by Cyrus et al.^{100, 101} showed that the somatic growth of *T. gratilla* fed a pelleted diet supplemented with 20% (w/w) dried *Ulva* was similar to animals fed fresh *Ulva*, but urchins fed with the pelleted feed had larger gonads/gonad somatic index. The findings of the present study support the findings of Cyrus et al.^{100, 101}, and once again demonstrate that feeds with a higher protein content support increased gonad yield. Moreover, these findings demonstrate that it is possible to feed urchins fresh *Ulva* during the somatic growth phase, and that feeding with protein rich formulated feeds, that are often more costly and less sustainable, is only required during the gonad enhancement phase to bulk gonads prior to market. The reduced somatic growth of urchins fed with *E. maxima* could be attributed to the fact that *Ecklonia* is not the preferred seaweed for this species. Cyrus et al.¹⁰² previously demonstrated in paired preference tests that *Ulva* was the most preferred algal species for *T. gratilla*, followed by *Ecklonia maxima*, *Porphyra capensis* and *Gigartina polycarpa*. *Ecklonia* also does not occur within the natural distribution range of *T. gratilla*, and may contain compounds that affect protein digestibility, palatability and growth of *Tripneustes*. The consumption rates of *U. lacinulata* and the formulated feed supplemented with 20% (w/w) dried *U. lacinulata* are also similar to what has been reported previously for our local *Tripneustes*^{102, 103}, and additional trials on feeding frequency confirmed that feeding *T. gratilla* a diet of fresh *Ulva* at ca. 7% of their body weight frequently (daily) produced the highest specific growth rates.

On-going trials in the pilot commercial sea urchin-*Ulva* IMTA have confirmed many of the previous findings obtained from smaller scale research trials conducted at the DFFE Marine Research Aquarium in Sea point (Cape Town). Most notably, somatic growth rates of urchins fed the three formulated feeds supplemented with seaweed(s) and fresh IMTA grown *Ulva* were similar during the somatic growth phase of the trials, once again confirming that it is possible to feed urchins with only fresh *U.*

⁹⁹ Cyrus M.D., Bolton J.J., Macey B.M., De Wet L., 2014. The development of a formulated feed containing *Ulva* (Chlorophyta) to promote rapid growth and enhanced production of high quality roe in the sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla* (Linnaeus). *Aquaculture Research* 45:159-176.

¹⁰⁰ Cyrus M.D., Bolton J.J., Macey B.M., De Wet L., 2014. The development of a formulated feed containing *Ulva* (Chlorophyta) to promote rapid growth and enhanced production of high quality roe in the sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla* (Linnaeus). *Aquaculture Research* 45:159-176.

¹⁰¹ Cyrus, M.D., Bolton, J.J., Macey, B.M., 2015. The role of the green seaweed *Ulva* as a dietary supplement for full life-cycle grow-out of *Tripneustes gratilla*. *Aquaculture* 446:187-197.

¹⁰² Cyrus, M.D., Bolton, J.J., Macey, B.M., 2015. The role of the green seaweed *Ulva* as a dietary supplement for full life-cycle grow-out of *Tripneustes gratilla*. *Aquaculture* 446:187-197.

¹⁰³ Cyrus M.D., Bolton J.J., Scholtz R., Macey B.M., 2015. The advantages of *Ulva* (Chlorophyta) as an additive in sea urchin formulated feeds: effects on palatability, consumption and digestibility. *Aquaculture Nutrition*. 21:578-591.

lacunculata during the somatic growth phase and obtain similar test diameters prior to the gonad enhancement phase (Table 2). For farms capable of growing *Ulva*, particularly in an integrated system where *Ulva* is grown utilising the dissolved ammonia nitrogen excreted by the urchins, the use of fresh *Ulva* alone as a feed during the somatic growth phase provides economic and environmental benefits — in addition to improved system functionality and welfare of animals. The growth rates of urchins achieved in the pilot commercial IMTA (0.287 mm.d^{-1}) are in line with previous studies for *T. gratilla*. Although slightly lower than the SGR reported by Cyrus et al.¹⁰⁴ (0.38 mm.d^{-1}), they are higher than the SGRs of *T. gratilla* reported by Shpigel et al.¹⁰⁵. It is also worth noting that the stocking densities (ca. 8 kg.m^{-2}) of the present trial are significantly higher compared to the Cyrus et al.¹⁰⁴ (initial stocking density of 0.11 kg.m^{-2}) and Shpigel et al.¹⁰⁵ (final stocking density of 7.73 kg.m^{-2}) studies. This is extremely encouraging considering that this trial was conducted under commercial conditions as opposed to the research-based trials of Cyrus et al.¹⁰⁴ and Shpigel et al.¹⁰⁵. Since these trials are still on-going, it is not possible at this stage to comment on the quality and yield of the gonads from urchins fed the different formulated feeds and feeding regimes.

Table 2. Summary of optimal value for the various parameters investigated in this study for the commercial cultivation of warm water sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla*.

Parameter	Optimal value
Density	$\pm 20\%$ coverage of available ISA* of basket
Basket depth	< 20 cm
Feed	Fresh <i>Ulva</i> during the somatic growth phase, and formulated feeds, supplemented with 20% (w/w) dried <i>Ulva</i> during the gonad enhancement phase
Basket removal time	< 30 seconds
Measurement device	Computer vision protocol significantly increases precision and decreases time required for estimating average urchin diameter and mass
Salinity	30-25 ppt

*ISA = internal surface area

¹⁰⁴ Cyrus M .D., 2013. The use of *Ulva* as a feed supplement in the development of an artificial diet and feeding regimes to produce export quality roe from the sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla* (Linnaeus), PhD, pp 230. University of Cape Town, South Africa.

¹⁰⁵ Shpigel M., Shauli L., Odintsov V., Ashkenazi N., Ben-Ezra D., 2018. *Ulva lactuca* biofilter from a land-based integrated multi trophic aquaculture (IMTA). Aquaculture 496:221-231.
system as a sole food source for the tropical sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla elatensis*. Aquaculture 496:221-231.

4.3 Urchin *Parechinus angulosus* integrated with juvenile abalone *Haliotis midae*

4.3.1 Introduction

The high value abalone species, *Haliotis midae*, and the Cape sea urchin, *Parechinus angulosus*, have a similar preferred temperature range (12-20°C)^{106,107,108} and commonly occur together in nature, particularly during the juvenile stages of the abalone life cycle¹⁰⁹. The Cape sea urchin is a generalist herbivore found along the South African coastline¹¹⁰. During the early post-settlement stages of the abalone *Haliotis midae*, there is a known ecological relationship between *P. angulosus* and juvenile *H. midae* in nature, where the urchins provide the juvenile abalone with shelter and protection from predators.

However, shelter and protection might not be the only driver of the positive relationship between these species. Other factors, such as improved food supply¹¹¹ and provision of beneficial bacterial communities from *P. angulosus* faeces could be playing advantageous roles in the development of juvenile abalone^{112,113}. Across various marine invertebrates, enteric bacteria are thought to play roles in the synthesis of essential amino acids¹¹⁴, provisioning of digestive enzymes, improvement of digestive efficiency^{115, 116, 117}, nitrogen metabolism, as well as in the acquisition of essential

¹⁰⁶ Fricke A.H., 1980. Aspects of population structure of *Parechinus Angulosus* Leske, around the Cape Peninsula. South African Journal of Zoology 15:177-185.

¹⁰⁷ Britz P.J., Hecht T., Mangold S., 1997. Effect of temperature on growth, feed consumption and nutritional indices of *Haliotis midae* fed a formulated diet. Aquaculture 152:191-203.

¹⁰⁸ Day E., Branch G.M., 2002a. Influences of the sea urchin *Parechinus angulosus* (Leske) on the feeding behaviour and activity rhythms of juveniles of the South African abalone *Haliotis midae* Linn. Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology 276:1-17.

¹⁰⁹ Day E., Branch G.M., 2000. Relationships between recruits of abalone *Haliotis midae*, encrusting corallines and the sea urchin *Parechinus angulosus*. South African Journal of Marine Science 22:137-144.

¹¹⁰ Greenwood P.J., 1975. Population dynamics and ecological energetics of *Parechinus angulosus* at Robben Island and False Bay, South Africa. MSc Thesis, University of Cape Town, Cape Town, South Africa.

¹¹¹ Day E., Branch G.M., 2002b. Effects of sea urchins (*Parechinus angulosus*) on recruits and juveniles of abalone (*Haliotis midae*). Ecological Monographs 72:133-149.

¹¹² Garland C.D., Cooke S.L., Grant J.F., McMeekin T.A., 1985. Ingestion of the bacteria on and the cuticle of crustose (non-articulated) coralline algae by post-larval and juvenile abalone (*Haliotis ruber* Leach) from Tasmanian waters. Journal of Experimental Marine Biology and Ecology 91:137-149.

¹¹³ Sweijd N.A., 1990. The digestive mechanisms of an intertidal grazer, the sea urchin *Parechinus angulosus*. MSc thesis, Rhodes University, Grahamstown, South Africa.

¹¹⁴ Fong W., Mann K., 1980. Role of gut flora in the transfer of amino acids through a marine food chain. Canadian Journal of Fisheries and Aquatic Science 37: 88-96.

¹¹⁵ Prim P., Lawrence J.M., 1975. Utilization of marine plants and their constituents by bacteria isolated from the gut of Echinoida (Echinodermata). Marine Biology 33:167-173.

¹¹⁶ ten Doeschate K.I., Coyne V.E., 2008. Improved growth rate in farmed *Haliotis midae* through probiotic treatment. Aquaculture 284:174-179.

¹¹⁷ Zhao J., Ling Y., Zhang R., Ke C., Hong G., 2018. Effects of dietary supplementation of probiotics on growth, immune responses, and gut microbiome of the abalone *Haliotis diversicolor*. Aquaculture 493:289-295.

micronutrients¹¹⁸. A co-culturing concept has been assessed for sea cucumbers (*Apostichopus japonicus*) and juvenile abalone (*Haliotis discus hannai*), where the sea cucumbers feed on the food residues and faecal matter produced by the abalone¹¹⁹. Considering co-habitation of sea urchins and juvenile abalone in natural environments, as well as the potential symbiotic relationships that exist between them, they could be co-cultured as a method of improving animal health through the trophic transfer of microbial communities. These species are therefore strong candidates for IMTA, with hatchery-produced abalone benefiting from sea urchin faecal matter supplementation during early juvenile stages as the transfer of microbial communities could aid in digestion, growth and overall health.

The implementation of IMTA can increase the efficiency of aquaculture systems and contribute to the development of a sustainable aquaculture industry, particularly when species that are ecologically compatible are co-cultured. The co-culture of these species has not previously been assessed and optimisation of sea urchin-abalone integration was required before assessing the effects of sea urchin faecal matter supplementation on juvenile abalone. Additionally, the feasibility of the Cape sea urchin as an additional value-added product has not been investigated as yet. Therefore, the objectives of the trials described below were as follows: (i) optimise sea urchin-abalone integrated aquaculture configuration (Trial 1 & 2), (ii) assess the effects of using sea urchin faecal matter as a feed for juvenile abalone on abalone health, welfare, growth, gut enzymology and development (Trial 1 - 3), (iii) investigate the microbial communities associated with the integrated aquaculture of these species, as well as their potential transfer between trophic levels (Trial 3), (iv) assess the microbiome data for biosecurity risks associated with this practice (Trial 3) and (v) assess the effects of different temperatures and feeding regimes on the growth performance of the Cape sea urchin species (Trial 4).

4.3.2 Trial Methodology

Trial 1 – Optimisation of sea urchin and juvenile abalone co-cultivation at the Marine Research Aquarium

Prior to conducting co-habitation trials, wild sea urchins collected from Sea Point (directly in front of the MRA) were acclimated to the aquarium environment for a month and fed *Ulva lacunculata ad libitum* for the duration of the acclimatisation. All live animal holding tanks were well-aerated, a

¹¹⁸ Phillips N.W., 1984. Role of different microbes and substrates as potential suppliers of specific, essential nutrients to marine detritivores. *Bulletin of Marine Science* 35:283-298.

¹¹⁹ Kim T., Yoon H.S., Shin S., Oh M.H., Kwon I., Lee J., et al., 2015. Physical and biological evaluation of co-culture cage systems for grow-out of juvenile abalone, *Haliotis discus hannai*, with juvenile sea cucumber, *Apostichopus japonicus* (Selenka), with CFD analysis and indoor seawater tanks. *Aquaculture* 447:86-101.

photoperiod of 12h:12h light: dark was maintained and tanks were cleaned on a daily basis or as needed. Following acclimation, sea urchins with a diameter of ca. 5cm were stocked at different densities (1, 2 and 3 kg.m⁻²), without any juvenile abalone, to assess faecal matter production in glass tanks (46cm×23cm×30 cm, L×W×D; 0.56m² to fill volume) (Figure 36). The results from this short trial were used to inform the first sea urchin-abalone co-habitation trial and the higher sea urchin stocking density of 3 kg.m⁻² was used to stock tanks to ensure the availability of faecal matter as a food source for the juvenile abalone.

Figure 36. Experimental design for first optimisation trial for the use of faecal matter from the Cape sea urchin *Parechinus angulosus* as feed for newly depleted juvenile abalone, which was conducted at the Marine Research Aquarium in Sea Point.

A preliminary co-habitation trial was conducted in a temperature-controlled (16°C) laboratory at the MRA for two months to assess different configurations for the urchins (n=108; n=12 per tank across 9 tanks) with juvenile abalone with a shell length < 3 mm (n=1800; n=200 per tank across 12 tanks). All

juvenile abalone were obtained from Buffeljags Abalone Farm and were transported to the MRA in bags supplemented with oxygenated water in Styrofoam containers fitted with ice packs and moist sponge. All juvenile abalone were from the same batch of animals (i.e., the same parent pairs were used to establish the juvenile abalone and they were collected from the same settlement tank to avoid tank/parental effects). See ASTRAL deliverable 2.8 for more details on abalone larval and juvenile stages. The experimental design was as follows (Figure 36): 3 control tanks with only juvenile abalone that were being fed a formulated feed at standard farm feeding rates; 3 tanks with juvenile abalone under sea urchins that were held in oyster-mesh baskets (6mm) to allow faecal matter to fall through the baskets to the base of the tank where the juvenile abalone are housed; 3 tanks with sea urchins in baskets above the abalone where the abalone were also being fed a formulated feed; and lastly, 3 tanks with juvenile abalone in direct contact with sea urchins (no baskets in tanks). Animal welfare, growth and survival was assessed for both the sea urchins and juvenile abalone for two months.

Trial 2 – Optimisation of sea urchin and juvenile abalone co-cultivation at Buffeljags Abalone Farm

A trial was conducted on Buffeljags Abalone Farm to verify juvenile abalone growth and survival benefits observed in the trial conducted at the MRA (Trial 1), as well as to up-scale the co-cultivation of abalone and sea urchins. The sea urchins used in this trial were collected from Buffeljags Bay. This trial included a total of 72 sea urchins (*P. angulosus*; average weight = 71.60 ± 5.17 g; average diameter = 5.46 ± 0.13 cm) with $n = 24$ across 3 tanks (50cm×50cm×25 cm, L×W×D) where sea urchins were held in baskets above juvenile abalone ($n = 800$ per tank) (Figure 37). Three control tanks, identical in dimensions to the sea urchin-abalone tanks, were included in the trial with $n = 800$ juvenile abalone per tank, resulting in a total of 4800 juvenile abalone included in the trial. The juvenile abalone in the control tanks were fed a mixed diet of diatoms and a formulated feed. The inclusion of diatoms was necessary as Trial 1 showed that the newly depleted juvenile abalone required an additional food source prior to the introduction of formulated feed. Juvenile abalone growth and survival was monitored for the duration of the trial.

Figure 37. Experimental design for second optimisation trial for the use of faecal matter from the Cape sea urchin *Parechinus angulosus* as feed for newly depleted juvenile abalone, which was conducted on Buffeljags Abalone Farm.

Trial 3 – Large-scale sea urchin and juvenile abalone co-cultivation at Buffeljags Abalone Farm

The results and observations from the optimisation trials (Trial 1 & Trial 2) were used to inform a large-scale trial in the Buffeljags Abalone Farm hatchery. An 8-week trial was conducted at the farm, where two sets of three tanks, each tank (0.68 m×0.50 m×0.12 m; LxWxD) with 25000 juvenile abalone with starting shell lengths of ca. 3 mm that were fed a mixed diet of diatoms, formulated feed, *Ulva lacinulata* and *Gracilaria* (Figure 38). One set of abalone tanks was only fed the mixed diet (control) and the other set was provided with a daily supplement of sea urchin faecal matter collected from 310 sea urchins per tank. Sea urchins were only fed *U. lacinulata* and were held in baskets in separate tanks (0.68 m×0.50 m×0.12 m; LxWxD) as preliminary trials indicated that this simplifies animal husbandry practices for these species.

Figure 38. Experimental design for large-scale trial for the use of faecal matter from the Cape sea urchin *Parechinus angulosus* as feed for newly depleted juvenile abalone, which was conducted on Buffeljags Abalone Farm.

Juvenile abalone growth and survival was monitored for the duration of the trial. Abalone growth was assessed by measuring shell length and width (in cm) of 300 randomly chosen animals per tank at each timepoint (0 weeks, 1 week, 4 weeks and 8 weeks). After the conclusion of the faecal matter supplementation trial, abalone were moved to the next phases of the grow-out cycle, where they were all fed the same feeds and additional abalone size measurements were taken at the 16-week and 26-week timepoint to assess differences in grow-out performance for abalone that received the faecal matter versus those that did not (control). Survival was assessed weekly for the duration of the 8-week trial by collecting and counting mortalities (shells) from the tanks. Abalone gut enzymatic (amylase and protease) activity was assessed by collecting and immediately freezing ca. 10-30 juvenile abalone from each tank once a month at -20°C until further processed.

Lastly, the transfer of microbial communities (bacteria, fungi and oomycetes) from the sea urchins to the abalone was assessed using a 16S rDNA and ITS2 next-generation sequencing (NGS) approach and sequence data processed as described in Section 6.1.2, Trial 2. Microbiome samples (n=75) included the incoming seawater (500 mL per replicate sample) that was collected on 0.22 µm filters, sea urchin intestines and faecal matter, abalone intestines and faecal matter, as well as each of the feeds used to feed the sea urchins (*U. lacinulata*) and juvenile abalone (sea urchin faecal matter, diatoms, formulated feed, *U. lacinulata*, *Gracilaria*).

Trial 4 – Assessing somatic growth and gonad development of the Cape sea urchin to evaluate the potential of Cape urchin gonads as an additional product.

The sea urchins (*Parechinus angulosus*) were collected from in front of the Marine Research Aquarium in Sea Point (n = 650). Approximately 5 urchins were sacrificed upon collection and prior to the start of the experiment to assess gonad condition prior to starting the trial. After a 3-week acclimatisation period, the sea urchins were divided into oyster mesh baskets (6 mm mesh size; 40x29x16 cm; LxWxD) suspended in flow-through tanks (42x36x30 cm; LxWxD; volume = 40 L; flow rate at a rate of ~ 1000 L.min⁻¹) at 19 sea urchins (individual diameter of ca. 4 cm) per basket.

Four feeding regimes were tested in quadruplicate in this trial: *Ulva lacunculata* (U), *Ecklonia maxima* kelp (K), a formulated feed containing 16% *Ulva* (F), as well as a rotation of the diets (U, K, F) on a weekly basis to form a mixed diet (M) regime, resulting in a total of 16 tanks (n = 320 sea urchins). All feeds were administered *ad libitum* and the trial was conducted for six months. These feeding regimes were duplicated across two temperature treatments: ambient incoming temperature and 19°C. Data were collected throughout the trial to assess the feasibility of the Cape sea urchin as a value-added product for integrated aquaculture of the Cape sea urchin and juvenile abalone. These data included: (i) temperature; (ii) sea urchin weight (g) and diameter (cm); and (iii) gonad quality assessments.

4.3.3 Results

Trial 1 – Optimisation of sea urchin and juvenile abalone co-cultivation at the Marine Research Aquarium

Sea urchin faecal matter production and growth

Sea urchin faecal matter was collected across the stocking densities tested in this trial (1, 2 and 3 kg.m⁻²) and it was observed that the highest stocking density tested (3 kg.m⁻²) produced 10.15±1.33 g (wet weight, equivalent to 0.15 g dry weight) of faecal matter. It was observed that there was improved dispersion of feed in the tank (given the larger amount of faecal matter produced) at the higher stocking density and therefore, this was selected as the stocking density for the first sea urchin-abalone co-habitation trial at the MRA in Sea Point. Sea urchin diameter (cm) and weight (g) were monitored for the duration of the first co-habitation trial, but no significant urchin growth was observed over the two-month trial period.

Juvenile abalone growth, survival and husbandry

Tanks with sea urchins held in baskets above juvenile abalone and where the abalone were supplemented with a formulated feed was shown to be preferable, as the abalone displayed the greatest growth rate during the 2-month trial and had statistically significantly larger shells at week 6 (Figure 39A; $P < 0.05$; ANOVA) and greater growth rates at week 6 (Figure 39B; $P < 0.05$; ANOVA). Towards the end of the trial (week 8), lower average shell length was observed for abalone fed only a formulated feed, though this observation was not statistically significant. In terms of animal husbandry, it was found that the urchins held in baskets above abalone, rather than in direct contact with the abalone, simplifies co-habitation of sea urchins and juvenile abalone as juvenile abalone require tanks to be cleaned daily or every second day. The trial was limited by the lack of wild diatoms as a feed for juvenile abalone in the early stages (1-2 weeks) after depleting from the settlement substrate as survival was ca. 30% during the first month of the trial, although this could also have occurred as a result of stress during transport to the research aquarium. Regardless, limited differences in survival were observed between dietary treatments during this time-period, or between month 1 and 2 (ca. 80% survival). To account for the lack of diatoms and the impact of transport that could have affected initial juvenile abalone survival, diatoms were included in Trial 2 and the trial was carried out at Buffeljags Abalone Farm to avoid transportation and to assess the use of faecal matter as a feed for juvenile abalone in a farm context.

Figure 39. Juvenile abalone (A) shell length (mm) and (B) cumulative shell length specific growth rate (% growth per day) across dietary treatments. AF: abalone fed formulated feed (control); AUB: abalone under urchins that were kept in baskets; AUBF: abalone that were supplemented with formulated feed and held under urchins in baskets; AU: abalone in direct contact with urchins.

Trial 2 – Optimisation of sea urchin and juvenile abalone co-cultivation at Buffeljags Abalone Farm

Juvenile abalone growth, survival and husbandry

In Trial 2 the survival rate was 65.5% and 70% for the abalone fed a formulated feed and diatoms (AF), and for abalone fed a formulated feed, diatoms and were supplemented with sea urchin faecal matter (AUBF), respectively. Shell length was similar for the treatment groups throughout the trial (Figure 40A). A higher growth rate was observed for the animals supplemented with faeces over the 2-month period, although these differences were not statistically significant (Figure 40B; $P > 0.05$; ANOVA). This trial was carried out at Buffeljags Abalone Farm, which runs a commercial abalone hatchery, and it is not feasible to maintain and clean tanks that hold both sea urchins and juvenile abalone at a commercial hatchery scale. Additionally, the formulated feed and diatoms used as a feed for juvenile abalone was administered more effectively without the urchins in the tank. Therefore, the subsequent and final trial (Trial 3) was carried out by collecting faecal matter from sea urchins housed in separate tanks.

Figure 40. Juvenile abalone (A) shell length (mm) and (B) cumulative shell length specific growth rate (% growth per day) across dietary treatments. AF: abalone fed formulated feed and diatoms (control); AUBF: abalone that were supplemented with formulated feed, diatoms and sea urchin faeces from urchin held in baskets above them.

Trial 3 – Large-scale sea urchin and juvenile abalone co-cultivation at Buffeljags Abalone Farm

Juvenile abalone growth, survival and performance

Results from the commercial-scale trial showed that the shell length of juvenile abalone were statistically significantly larger ($P < 0.05$; one-way ANOVA) throughout the 2-month trial (Figure 41). After the trial the juvenile abalone were moved to the next stages of grow-out as per the farm’s standard practices, where the abalone from the control tanks and the tanks supplemented with sea urchin faeces were fed the same mixed diet, but animals were held in separate tanks so that growth could be monitored. It was observed that the animals supplemented with faecal matter remained larger than the control group for up to 8-weeks after the trial concluded, but were similar in size 10 weeks after that, though this could have been influenced by size-grading as the animals move through the various stages of production. Notably, the maximum abalone shell sizes recorded were observed for the group of animals that were supplemented with faecal matter during the first 8-weeks after settlement, with a maximum length of 3.11 cm and 3.85 cm recorded after 26-weeks for the control and faecal matter treatment animals, respectively.

Figure 41. Average juvenile abalone shell length (cm) over a duration of 8 weeks across abalone fed only diatoms, a formulated feed, *Ulva* and *Gracilaria* (control, n=300 per time point) and abalone fed diatoms, a formulated feed, *Ulva* and *Gracilaria* while being supplemented with sea urchin faeces (n=300 per time point), with an additional two measurement points after the conclusion of the feeding trial at 16- and 26-weeks.

The abalone supplemented with sea urchin faecal matter displayed improved survival over the course of the study with an overall 5% higher survival rate observed for animals supplemented with faecal matter at the end of the 8-week feeding trial. This benefit was particularly evident in the latter half of

the experiment (Figure 42), possibly as a result of the transfer of microbial communities from the sea urchins to the juvenile abalone.

Figure 42. Average juvenile abalone survival over the 8-week trial period across abalone fed only diatoms, a formulated feed, *Ulva* and *Gracilaria* (control, n=300 per time point) and abalone fed diatoms, a formulated feed, *Ulva* and *Gracilaria* while being supplemented with sea urchin faeces (n=300 per time point), with an additional survival assessment one week after the conclusion of the feeding trial.

Microbial communities associated with sea urchin-juvenile abalone co-cultivation

The most dominant phyla identified in this study included Proteobacteria (45%), Bacteroidota (32%) and Fusobacteriota (6%). The most abundant bacterial genera included *Vibrio* (8%), *Psychromonas* (8%) and a genus belonging to the family Rhodobacteraceae (7%), *Tenacibaculum* (6%) and *Formosa* (5%) (Figure 43). The sea urchin intestinal tract was dominated by *Psychromonas* (39%), an uncultured Arcobacteraceae genus (27%) and *Roseimarinus* (10%), whereas the sea urchin faecal matter was dominated by the genera *Psychromonas* (33%), *Propionigenium* (12%) and *Roseimarinus* (10%). The dominant bacteria in the intestines of juvenile abalone fed the sea urchin faecal matter were *Psychromonas* (29%), *Formosa* (10%) and *Propionigenium* (7%), while the control animals were dominated by *Formosa* (36%), *Psychrilyobacter* (11%) and *Vibrio* (11%). Notably, a reduction in the genus *Vibrio* was observed when comparing the control (11%) and treatment (6%) juvenile abalone.

Figure 43. Bacterial genera associated with the feeds sampled, the incoming water, the sea urchin intestines, juvenile abalone that received the faecal matter supplement (T1-T2), the juvenile abalone only fed the mixed feeding regime without faecal matter (C1-C2), as well as the sea urchin and abalone faecal matter. Numbers in sample IDs represent sampling points (months).

A transfer of bacterial communities was observed from the urchins to their faecal matter, as well as from the faecal matter to the juvenile abalone towards the end of the feeding trial. While fungal identification was not possible as a result of the limited marine fungi that have been previously characterised and are available in publicly available databases, the bacterial microbiome dynamics could be tracked across the samples collected from this trial. Overall, 62 bacterial genera were transferred to the abalone from sea urchin faeces (Figure 44).

Figure 44. Venn diagram depicting the number of bacterial genera shared across the sea urchin faecal matter (n=3), the juvenile abalone supplemented with faeces (n=9) and juvenile abalone not supplemented with faeces (control; n=9) at the 2-month sampling point.

Trial 4 – Assessing somatic growth rate and gonad development of the Cape sea urchin to evaluate the potential of Cape urchin gonads as an additional product

Sea urchin survival

The potential for the Cape sea urchin as aquaculture product was assessed and it was observed that sea urchin survival was lower for animals fed kelp (*E. maxima*) (Figure 45). As the animals fed kelp displayed continued loss of spines and lesions on the exoskeleton, this feeding regime (K) was excluded from the trial and was no longer included in the mixed feeding (M) regime after 9-weeks. The mixed feeding regime included only *Ulva lacinulata* and the formulated feed (rotated on a weekly basis) from week 10 onwards. No significant differences in survival were observed for any of the other feeding regimes. However, statistically significantly ($P < 0.01$) higher survival was observed for animals reared in the warmed water tanks across all dietary treatments. The average temperature over the entire experimental period was (mean \pm SE) 15.36 \pm 0.01 $^{\circ}$ C (range=12.33-18.62 $^{\circ}$ C) and 18.88 \pm 0.01 $^{\circ}$ C (range=17.06-19.92 $^{\circ}$ C) for the ambient and heated systems, respectively.

Figure 45. Cape sea urchin average percentage (%) survival over the 24 week feeding trial across dietary treatments (formulated feed, kelp, mixed and *Ulva*) and temperature conditions (ambient and warmed). Letters above bars represent dietary treatment groups that are significantly different to each other based on Dunn’s test with Bonferroni correction. Hashtags above bars indicate the level of significant difference between temperature treatment groups based on Mann-Whitney U tests (#: $P < 0.05$, ##: $P < 0.01$, ###: $P < 0.001$). No letters or hashtags indicate no significant differences.

Sea urchin somatic and gonad growth

Across the feeding regimes included in this trial, the sea urchin fed the formulated feed containing 16% *Ulva* showed the greatest specific growth rate (SGR; % growth per day) at the start of the trial (weeks 4-8) (Figure 46). However, the mixed feeding regime outperformed the other dietary treatments from week 13 onwards. Overall, the greatest gonad somatic index (GSI) was observed for formulated feed fed animals (Figure 47). Notably, the urchins fed kelp had little to no gonad development 9-weeks into the feeding trial, further supporting that kelp was not a suitable feed for the Cape sea urchin, at least at this life stage. The *Ulva* fed animals had the lowest GSI throughout the trial with the highest level of gonad maturity, but an increase in GSI was observed across all dietary treatments included until the end of the trial.

Figure 46. Cape sea urchin specific growth rate (%) per day for body weight (g) across dietary treatments (formulated feed with 16% *Ulva*, kelp, *Ulva lacinulata* and a mixed feeding regime) and temperature treatments (ambient and warmed) over time. Letters above bars represent dietary treatment groups that are significantly different to each other based on ANOVA, followed by Tukey's, post hoc pairwise comparison test respectively. Stars above bars indicate the level of significant difference between temperature treatment groups (*P<0.05, **P<0.01, ***P<0.001). No letters or stars indicate no significant differences.

Figure 47. Cape sea urchin gonad somatic index (GSI; %) across dietary treatments (formulated feed with 16% *Ulva*, kelp, *Ulva lacunculata* and a mixed feeding regime) and temperature treatments (ambient and warmed) over time. Letters above bars represent dietary treatment groups that are significantly different to each other based on ANOVA, followed by Tukey's, post hoc pairwise comparison test respectively.

4.3.4 Discussion and Conclusion

The preliminary optimisation trials (Trial 1 & 2) showed best growth rates for juvenile abalone that received the sea urchin faecal matter supplement, indicating that it could be acting as a functional feed for abalone in this early post-weaning life-stage. These Cape sea urchin and juvenile abalone (*Haliotis midae*) co-cultivation trials also showed that the sea urchins should be held separately from the abalone and faecal matter should be collected (siphoned) on a daily basis.

Although not statistically significantly different, there was an ca. 5% improvement in survival in Trial 2 and Trial 3 for abalone that received the faecal matter supplement. The growth results suggest that the faecal matter and possibly the microbes transferred from the urchins to the abalone provides an advantage in the early post-weaning stages. Using sea urchin faecal matter as a feed for juvenile abalone mimics the natural ecological relationship between these species along the South African coastline, and could be providing the juvenile abalone with enteric bacteria capable of synthesising digestive enzymes that could improve the digestive efficiency, nitrogen metabolism, as well as provide improved access to essential micronutrients.

The trophic transfer of microbial communities was assessed in this study and showed that both the treatment and control juvenile abalone had the presence of three genera commonly associated with the microbiome of adult abalone intestines, including *Psychrilyobacter*, *Vibrio* and *Mycoplasma*^{120,121}, but a reduction was observed for the opportunistic pathogen *Vibrio* — where there was a reduction in the intestines of juvenile abalone receiving the faecal matter as a feed. This is particularly beneficial given that the juvenile abalone are in a vulnerable life stage. Other microbiome-related benefits observed include the presence of *Psychromonas* and *Propionigenium* in the intestines of abalone fed the sea urchin faecal matter. *Psychromonas* is a known polyunsaturated fatty acid (PUFA)-producing bacteria¹²², and although abalone are also able to synthesise these compounds themselves it is known that they cannot synthesise sufficient amounts of PUFAs for maximum growth¹²³. *Propionigenium* has known anti-inflammatory roles through fatty acid synthesis¹²⁴, and also plays roles in energy metabolism¹²⁵ and fermentation¹²⁶ and can act in opposition to pathogenic bacteria.

Future work could investigate the impact of further increasing the amount of faecal matter fed to the juvenile abalone, or extending the time that it is fed to the juvenile abalone. Additionally, limited inferences can be made about the functional roles of the microbial communities identified in this trial and future studies should make use of shotgun metagenomics approaches to identify the functional roles of the resident microbiome and to better identify the other microbial communities (fungi, oomycetes, viruses) that may be transferred between the co-cultivated species.

The feasibility of the Cape sea urchin as an additional product from this co-cultivation was also assessed (Trial 4) and it was found that kelp (*Ecklonia maxima*) was not an optimal feed for this urchin species. It was also found that the sea urchins performed well in terms of growth, survival and gonad development when fed a mixed feeding regime of formulated feed (16% *Ulva* inclusion) and fresh *Ulva lacinulata*. However, the sea urchins were wild-collected and somatic growth was limited over the course of the trial (6 months). Therefore, it would be beneficial to assess growth and gonad

¹²⁰ Gobet A., Mest L., Perennou M., Dittami S.M., Caralp C., Coulombet C., et al., 2018. Seasonal and algal diet-drive patterns of the digestive microbiota of the European abalone *Haliotis tuberculata*, a generalist marine herbivore. *Microbiome* 6: 60.

¹²¹ Danckert N.P., Wilson N., Phan-Thien K.-Y., Stone D.A.J., 2021. The intestinal microbiome of Australian abalone, *Haliotis laevis* and *Haliotis laevis* × *Haliotis rubra*, over a 1-year period in aquaculture. *Aquaculture* 534:736245.

¹²² Shah A.M., Yang W., Mohamed H., Zhang Y., Song Y., 2022. Microbes: a hidden treasure of polyunsaturated fatty acids. *Frontiers in Nutrition* 9:827837.

¹²³ Xu W., Mai K.S., Ai Q.H., Tan B.P., Zhang W.B., Ma H.M., Liufu Z.G., 2011. Influence of 18:2n-6/20:5n3 ratio in diets on growth and fatty acid composition of juvenile red abalone, *Haliotis discus hannai* Ino. *Aquaculture Nutrition* 17:346351.

¹²⁴ Reichardt N., Duncan S.H., Young P., Belenguer A., Leitch C.M., Scott K.P., et al., 2014. Phylogenetic distribution of three pathways for propionate production within the human gut microbiota. *ISME Journal* 8:1323-1335.

¹²⁵ Schäfer G., 2013. Membrane-Associated Energy Transduction in Bacteria and Archaea; *Encyclopedia of Biological Chemistry*. 2nd Edition, Elsevier, Amsterdam, The Netherlands, pp. 28-35.

¹²⁶ Robinson G., Caldwell G., Wade M., Free A., Jones C.L.W. et al., 2016. Profiling bacterial communities associated with sediment-based aquaculture bioremediation systems under contrasting redox regimes. *Scientific Reports* 6:38850.

development for the Cape sea urchins that are hatchery-produced so that feeding regime can be assessed and optimised for the various life stages to maximise somatic growth prior to enhancing/bulking gonad.

In conclusion, supplementing juvenile abalone diets with sea urchin faecal matter is advantageous for abalone growth and health in their early juvenile stages, possibly as a result of microbial community transfer from the sea urchins. The intestinal microbiome is often established during the juvenile stages for aquatic animals and could have long-lasting effects on digestion, overall performance and health, possibly through the microbial provisioning of digestive enzymes. Further research is required to better understand the microbial community dynamics in the co-cultivation of juvenile abalone and sea urchins, as well as for the potential of Cape sea urchin aquaculture and marketability.

5. ASTRAL IMTA Production Species/Production Value Chain

IMTA Lab South Africa focused on the development and validation of cost effective IMTA in land-based pump ashore systems with partial recirculation. Trials took place at an existing fully commercial abalone farm, Buffeljags Abalone, which annually produces approximately 450 tons of the abalone *Haliotis midae* and 600 tons of the green seaweed *Ulva lacunculata* in the integrated systems. Buffeljags Abalone has successfully practiced this form of IMTA for more than a decade, and together with Diamond Coast Abalone, is one of only two farms in South Africa that currently practice IMTA. Both farms are subsidiaries of the Viking Aquaculture group. A paucity of information on the physical and chemical parameters of these IMTA systems, as well as biosecurity concerns associated with water recirculation and use of effluent-grown *Ulva* as a feed or functional feed ingredient, has however prevented wider adoption of this technology on other abalone farms in South Africa and abroad. These gaps in knowledge were a primary incentive for undertaking the research described in this deliverable.

Data generated from the various trials conducted at IMTA Lab South Africa has provided critical information on the physical and chemical parameters of the existing integrated abalone (*Haliotis midae*)-*Ulva lacunculata* IMTA system with 50% recirculation, including the microbial community, to provide critical information on biosecurity, species health and system health. The microbiome studies revealed a high diversity of bacteria in all compartments of the IMTA and associated with the species grown within the IMTA and revealed that the inclusion of *Ulva* in IMTA systems results in beneficial changes in the microbiome of water and farmed abalone in the system by reducing the presence of opportunistic pathogens. Trials further demonstrated that it is possible to increase recirculation in the IMTA to 75% for extended periods, without compromising the health of the animals in the system,

and 100% recirculation is possible for short periods of time (up to 3-days). Full (100%) recirculation is highly beneficial as it can provide much needed protection to abalone farms from Harmful Algal Bloom (HAB) events ('red tides'), which have caused devastating impacts to the local industry in recent years and HAB events appear to be increasing in prevalence along the South African coast¹²⁷. When assessing the bacterial community dynamics with increasing recirculation rates, it was shown that recirculation at higher rates (50%, 75% & 100%) has an effect on the microbiome composition, but does not result in an increase in opportunistic bacteria — likely as similar patterns were observed in terms of the modulatory effect of *Ulva* on the water microbiome. The inclusion of fresh IMTA grown *Ulva* or components of *Ulva* in formulated feeds for farmed abalone further support the effect of *Ulva* on the microbiome, as a reduction in opportunistic bacteria was observed in the digestive tracts of abalone consuming these feeds, with a corresponding increase in beneficial bacteria. These observations support findings reported previously in the literature on the benefits of including seaweed in the diet of cultured abalone^{128,129,130,131}. However, the present trials have provided empirical evidence for the first time on the positive impact of *Ulva* on the microbiome of an integrated abalone-*Ulva* system with varying recirculation rates. These finding will aid in promoting broader uptake of these more sustainable aquaculture production technologies and aid in the promoting sustainable growth of the abalone sector both locally and globally.

Besides the observed benefits of *Ulva* on the microbiome, trials conducted at the South African lab have shown that *Ulva* provides several other benefits to the IMTA. The bioremediation ability of *Ulva* reduces nutrient release from farms into the sea, reduces reliance on harvesting natural seaweeds (e.g., kelps, an important feed on most abalone farms) and reduces dependence on the use of protein rich formulated feeds. At standard 50% recirculation in the abalone-*Ulva* IMTA, total ammonia nitrogen removal across the seaweed biofilters ranged from 65%-85% (mean 73%). This represents a significant reduction in the amount of total ammonia nitrogen that would have been release back to

¹²⁷ Pitcher, G.C., Foord, C.J., Macey, N.M., Mansfield, L., Mouton, A., Smith, M.E., Osmond, S.J., van der Molen, L., 2019. Devastating farmed abalone mortalities attributed to yessotoxin-producing dinoflagellates. *Harmful Algae* 81: 30-41.

¹²⁸ Bansemmer, M.S., Qin, J.G., Harris, J.O., Duong, D.N., Hai, T., Howarth, G.S., Stone, D.A.J., 2016. Growth and feed utilisation of greenlip abalone (*Haliotis laevis*) fed nutrient enriched macroalgae. *Aquaculture*. 452, 62–68.

¹²⁹ Kemp, J.O.G., Britz, P.J., Agüero, P.H.T., 2015. The effect of macroalgal, formulated and combination diets on growth, survival and feed utilisation in the red abalone *Haliotis rufescens*. *Aquaculture*. 448(C), 306–314.

¹³⁰ Mulvaney, W.J., Winberg, P.C., Adams, L., 2013. Comparison of macroalgal (*Ulva* and *Grateloupia* spp.) and formulated terrestrial feed on the growth and condition of juvenile abalone. *Journal of Applied Phycology*. 25(3), 815–824.

¹³¹ Naidoo, K., Maneveldt, G., Ruck, K., Bolton, J.J., 2006. A comparison of various seaweed-based diets and formulated feed on growth rate of abalone in a land-based aquaculture system. *Journal of Applied Phycology*. 18(3–5), 437–443.

the ocean in a monoculture system. The bioremediation ability of the seaweed also significantly reduces pumping costs by allowing partial recirculation of water to abalone and urchins from seaweed tanks. Moreover, *Ulva* grown in IMTA has a higher protein content, with an amino acid profile similar to that of fishmeal as well as a high mineral content, that can benefit grown of cultured abalone and urchins and potentially serve as a source of food for humans. When this effluent grown *Ulva* is used as a feed or a feed additive in the formulated feeds, our trials have shown that *Ulva* enhances the chemosensory properties of formulated feeds, significantly improves feed conversion ratio (FCR), feed consumption and digestible protein and energy intake by both abalone and sea urchins^{132,133,134}. Due to the existing pigments in the seaweed, e.g., carotenoids, such as β -carotene, our trials have demonstrated that dietary supplementation with *Ulva* improves the colour and marketable properties of urchin gonads¹³². Collectively, this integrated method of cultivating abalone and sea urchin with *Ulva* results in the production of high value seafood species, as well as valuable by-products (derived from the seaweed), in an economically and environmentally sustainable manner.

Additional key objectives of IMTA Lab South Africa were the development and refinement of culture technologies for the commercial production of a new high value species, the collector sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla*, and an investigation of the potential for the use of faecal matter from the Cape sea urchin *Parechinus angulosus* as a feed/probiotic for juvenile abalone. Diversification is regarded globally as vital to future growth and sustainability of the aquaculture sector. In South Africa, the aquaculture industry is presently dominated by a limited number of high value species (e.g., abalone, mussels, oysters, trout) and the main aquaculture export in terms of generating foreign income is, overwhelmingly, the supply of abalone to Asian markets. The development of a new highly lucrative export in the form of the sea urchin will therefore help diversify the local aquaculture sector and in so doing help contribute towards key national priorities that include food security, job creation, gross domestic product (GDP), poverty alleviation and rural development. Moreover, the development of new innovative practices that promote health and welfare of species cultivated in intensive production systems will promote sustainable development and social acceptability of the industry.

¹³² Cyrus M.D., Bolton J.J., Macey B.M., De Wet L. (2014). The development of a formulated feed containing *Ulva* (Chlorophyta) to promote rapid growth and enhanced production of high quality roe in the sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla* (Linnaeus). *Aquaculture Research* 45:159-176.

¹³³ Cyrus M.D., Bolton J.J., Scholtz R., Macey B.M. (2015). The advantages of *Ulva* (Chlorophyta) as an additive in sea urchin formulated feeds: effects on palatability, consumption and digestibility. *Aquaculture Nutrition*. 21:578-591.

¹³⁴ Brand M.J. (2023). *Ulva* as a functional feed: A practical investigation into the effects of *Ulva lacunculata* on the growth, consumption, health and gut microbiota of the farmed abalone *Haliotis midae*. PhD thesis, University of Cape Town, South Africa.

The echinoculture (sea urchin aquaculture) trials conducted at IMTA Lab South Africa took the culture technologies developed at a research scale for *T. gratilla* over the past decade by the DFFE and UCT and further refined these technologies for commercial scale production of larvae, juveniles and adults in a commercial IMTA system. The first pilot commercial scale sea urchin-*Ulva* IMTA was designed and successfully constructed at Buffeljags Abalone farm — based on the existing abalone-*Ulva* IMTA that has functioned successfully over the past decade. Trials in this commercial IMTA revealed that shallower baskets (<20 cm) enhance the production of *Tripneustes*, facilitating improved consumption of feeds and lowering spine loss. Additionally, specific feed types (e.g., *Ecklonia maxima*) and extended basket removal times (> 30s) during routine feeding and cleaning events were shown to increase spine loss and reduce growth of the urchins. To maximise somatic growth and gonad yield, stocking densities of ca. 20% coverage of the internal surface area of baskets is recommended, and it was shown that it is beneficial to feed urchins fresh IMTA grown *Ulva* during most of the somatic growth phase, with protein rich formulated feeds only required during the gonad enhancement phase to bulk gonads prior to market. To further streamline production and reduce stress on cultured urchins, a computer vision protocol was developed that significantly increases the precision and decreases the time required for estimating average urchin diameter and mass in a commercial setting. Environmental factors such as salinity and temperature play a major role in the distribution of natural sea urchin stocks and for the pantropical shallow water echinoid *Tripneustes*, freshwater inputs (rivers) along the coastline are regarded as a major barrier for the distribution of species within the genus¹³⁵. Trials conducted at the lab concluded that careful consideration must be made with regards to site selection when farming *T. gratilla*, as hypo-saline conditions (<30 ppt) increase stress and reduce disease resistance of this species. Therefore, sites located close to estuaries where salinities are either periodically or frequently impacted by rainfall events should be avoided. Trials have demonstrated that it is possible to produce large amounts of high-quality juveniles for commercial production and a detailed production manual for commercial cultivation of the tropical and temperate sea urchin, which includes the hatchery and nursery stages, has been produced (ASTRAL deliverable D2.8).

Besides the on-going trials in the pilot commercial urchin-*Ulva* IMTA in South Africa, which continue to provide critical information to support this new IMTA production species/value chain, an additional novel species combination has been developed at IMTA Lab SA — temperate sea urchin, *Parechinus angulosus*, are fed with the green seaweed *Ulva* and their faecal material is used as supplementary feed/probiotic for juvenile abalone, *Haliotis midae*, improving abalone growth/health and enhancing

¹³⁵ Lessios H.A., Kane J., Robertson D.R., 2003. Phylogeography of the pantropical sea urchin *Tripneustes*: Contrasting patterns of population structure between oceans. *Evolution* 57: 2026-2036.

circularity. When juvenile abalone diets are supplemented with sea urchin faecal matter, it was observed that growth and health of abalone is enhanced. This is most likely the result of microbial community transfer from the sea urchins to abalone, as a clear trophic transfer of microbial communities was observed in the trials. Since the intestinal microbiome is often established during the juvenile stages for aquatic animals, this observation could have important implication for health and welfare of cultivated abalone, providing long-lasting effects on digestion, overall performance, and health — possibly through the microbial provisioning of digestive enzymes. As a result of the beneficial association between the Cape sea urchin and juvenile abalone, Buffeljags Abalone have already adopted this practice as part of their standard hatchery procedures. The feasibility of the Cape sea urchin as an additional product from this co-cultivation is also currently being assessed and could potentially provide a new value added product for the farm should it be demonstrated that growth rates are sufficient and gonads produced are of suitable market quality.

In conclusion, the trials conducted at IMTA Lab South Africa have provided valuable information on biosecurity, species health and system health of the existing abalone-*Ulva* IMTA systems with 50% recirculation. Critical information on the physical and chemical parameters as well as the microbial community of the IMTA was generated that could promote broader uptake of IMTA by local and international producers and enhance the sustainability of this production species/value chain. Culture technology for commercial scale production of a new high value species, the collector sea urchin *Tripneustes gratilla*, was development and further optimised in IMTA systems, and the benefits of using faecal matter from the Cape sea urchin *Parechinus angulosus* as a feed/probiotic for juvenile abalone was clearly demonstrated — resulting in enhanced growth and health of juvenile abalone. These findings have contributed towards the development of new, sustainable, profitable and resilient value chains for IMTA production within ASTRAL and the framework of existing, emerging and potential Atlantic markets.

6. Acknowledgements

The authors would like to acknowledge the following colleagues for their contributions to the studies outlined in this deliverable [Section 6.1: Michael Geldart (Trial 1), Bridget Makhahlela (Trial 2), Morgan Brand (Trial 4), Teejaswani Bachoo & Tjale Ramashia (Trial 5); Section 6.2: Bas de Vos (Trial 1 & 2), Rifaat Aziz (Trial 3), Thomas Lamy (Trial 4, Task 2); Section 6.3: Aimee Cloete (Trial 3 & 4)]. The authors would like to thank the following people and institutions for the availability of samples and the use of facilities, as well as for their input on various aspects of the Trials described in this deliverable: Mark Cyrus, Nick Loubser, Michelle Loubser, Stephan Fourie, Viking Aquaculture, Buffeljags Abalone Farm, Department of Forestry, Fisheries and the Environment (DFFE) (RSA), the University of Cape Town

(UCT) Biological Sciences department, the Centre for Proteomics and Genomics Research (CPGR) Next-Generation Sequencing Facility and the University of Cape Town's ICTS High Performance Computing (HPC) team.